

Chadron M.Friesen B.Ameduri

Outstanding Telechelic Perfluoropolyalkylethers and Applications Therefrom

Chadron Mark Friesen^{1*} and Bruno Ameduri^{2*}

¹Department of Chemistry, Trinity Western University, Langley, British Columbia, V2Y 1Y1, Canada;

²Ingénierie et Architectures Macromoléculaires, Institut Charles Gerhardt, Ecole Nationale Supérieure de Chimie de Montpellier (UMR5253-CNRS), 8, rue de l'École Normale, 34296 Montpellier Cedex 5, France.

Table of Contents

Abbreviations	4
1. Introduction.....	6
2. Synthesis of Telechelic Perfluoropolyalkylethers (PFPAEs) diacylfluorides	9
2.1 Direct Fluorination of Alkyl Ethers.....	9
2.2 Anionic Ring-Opening Polymerization of Fluorinated Epoxides and Oxetanes	11
2.3 Radical Photo-oxidation of Perfluoroalkenes.....	12
3. Commercially Available Telechelic PFPAEs	15
4. Characterization and Properties of PFPAEs	16
4.1 Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) Spectroscopy.....	17
4.2 Mass Spectrometry.....	21
4.3 Chemical , Physical and Thermal Properties	22
4.3.1 Chemical Properties	22
4.3.2 Thermal Properties	23
4.3.3 Conclusion.....	25
4.4 Rheology	25
4.5 Lubricity	31
4.6 Chromatography.....	33
4.7 PFPAEs: Health and the Environment.....	33
4.8 Conclusion.....	35
5. Intermediate Telechelic PFPAEs for Materials	35
6. Materials based on Telechelic PFPAEs	38
6.1 Formation of Fluoroelastomers.....	38

6.1.1 Polycondensation reactions (polyurethanes, polyesters, polyamides, and polycarbonates) to form multiblock copolymers	38
6.1.2 Reactive Macromonomers for radical or photo-polymerization [telechelic bis(meth)acrylates and bisstyrenes]	42
6.2 Triblock or Multiblock Copolymer Materials	49
6.2.1 PEO- <i>b</i> -PFPE- <i>b</i> -PEO Triblock Copolymers	49
6.2.2 Synthesis of PFPE- <i>b</i> -PEO- <i>b</i> -PFPE triblock Copolymers	54
6.2.3 Synthesis of Poly(M)- <i>b</i> -PFPAE- <i>b</i> -Poly(M) triblock Copolymers from Telechelic PFPEs	55
6.3. Synthesis of cross-linked materials based on PFPAEs	57
6.3.1 Photocrosslinked telechelic bis(meth)acrylates for interpenetrated polymer networks (IPNs)	57
6.3.2 Alkyne-Azide “click” Chemistry with Trifunctional Derivatives	60
6.3.3 Polyhydrosilylation of Telechelic PFPAE dienes with Telechelic Bis(silane)	62
7. Applications of Telechelic PFPAEs	63
7.1 Self-Assembly Materials	63
7.2 Aerospace Materials	71
7.3. Microfluidic Devices	75
7.4 Low Surface Tension, Anti-Fouling, and De-icing Coatings	80
7.5 Optically and Antireflective Transparent Films	86
7.6 Self-Healing Materials	88
7.7 Thermoplastic Elastomers	91
7.8 Materials for Energy	93
7.9 Resistant Photoresists for Lithographic Materials	97
7.10 Theranostics	101
8. Conclusions and Perspectives	103
Acknowledgements	104
References	104

Outstanding Telechelic Perfluoropolyalkylethers and Applications Therefrom

Chadron Mark Friesen^{1*} and Bruno Ameduri^{2*}

¹Department of Chemistry, Trinity Western University, Langley, British Columbia, V2Y 1Y1, Canada;

²Ingénierie et Architectures Macromoléculaires, Institut Charles Gerhardt, Ecole Nationale Supérieure de Chimie de Montpellier (UMR5253-CNRS), 8, rue de l'École Normale, 34296 Montpellier Cedex 5, France.

Abstract

An overview on the synthesis and applications of telechelic perfluoropolyalkylethers (PFPAEs) is presented. First, a non-exhaustive summary on the synthesis and properties of commercially available PFPAEs is supplied, followed by conventional strategies for the preparation of telechelic PFPAEs ranging from direct fluorination, anionic ring-opening polymerization of oxetane and hexafluoropropylene oxide, to photochemical radical polymerization of tetrafluoroethylene, hexafluoropropene, or perfluoromethyl vinyl ether in the presence of oxygen. Properties (chemical, physical, and thermal) and characterizations (NMR, MALDI, rheology, lubricity, and toxicity) of these PFPAEs will also be presented. Telechelic PFPPFA bis(acylfluorides) are interesting precursors for a wide range of molecules and copolymers such as: polycondensates (polyesters, polyurethanes, polycarbonates, polyethers), macromonomers that can further be cross-linked, triblock copolymers, and (semi) interpenetrated polymer networks. Furthermore, important applications of these modified PFPAEs will be exhibited. These applications range from self-assembly materials (e.g. amphiphilic and anti-bacterial derivatives, and hydrogels), aerospace materials, microfluidic devices, protective coatings (e.g. low surface tension, anti-fouling, and de-icing), optically transparent films, self-healing materials, thermoplastic elastomers, materials for energy (e.g. zinc-air and lithium ion batteries, polymeric electrolyte membranes for fuel cells), resistant photoresists for lithographic materials, to theranostics (e.g. intracellular pH measurements and in vivo cell tracking technologies using Magnetic Resonance Imaging). This overview summarizes these emerging fields, emphasizing structural variety, end group functionalities, post-polymerization modifications, and applications previously unobtainable without accessible to these new materials.

Keywords: advanced materials, anionic ring-opening polymerization, fluoropolymers, perfluoropolyalkylethers, radical photo-oxidation, telechelics, thermal properties, well-defined materials

Abbreviations

AFM	atomic force microscopy
ARF	adhesion-reduction-factor
AIBN	azobisisobutyronitrile
Bar	barometric pressure
BDO	1,4-butandiol
BME	benzoin methyl ether
BPO	benzoyl peroxide
BVE	bisvinylether
CMC	critical micelle concentration
COSY	homonuclear correlation spectroscopy
cSt	centistokes
DBTDL	dibutyltin dilaurate
DC	dendritic cells
DCTB	<i>trans</i> -2-[3-(4- <i>tert</i> -butylphenyl)-2-methyl-2-propenylidene]malononitrile
DMA	dimethacrylate and dynamic mechanical analysis
DMT	dimethyl terephthalate
DMI	dimethyl isophthalate
DP _n	degree of polymerization in number
DOSY	diffusion-ordered spectroscopy
DSC	differential scanning calorimetry
EG	ethylene glycol
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
g·mol ⁻¹	grams per mole
GPTMS	(3-glycidylpropyl)trimethoxy silane
GPC	gel-permeation (or size-exclusion) chromatography
GPL	general purpose lubricant
HEA	2-hydroxyethyl acrylate
HFP	hexafluoropropene
HFPO	hexafluoropropylene oxide
HTC	high temperature conversion
ΔH _c	heat of combustion
ΔH _f	heat of fusion
IEM	2-isocyanatoethyl methacrylate
IPDI	isophorone diisocyanate
IPN	interpenetrated polymer network
kJ	kilojoule
LIB	lithium ion battery
LIMS	liquid injected molding silanes
LiTFSI	lithium bis(trifluoromethane sulfonyl)imide
LOC	lab-on-a-chip
MALDI	matrix assisted laser desorption ionization
M _c	“critical” molecular weight

meq·g ⁻¹	milliequivalent per gram (ion exchange capacity)
MDI	methylene diphenyl 4,4'-diisocyanate
mg·mL ⁻¹	milligram per milliliter (a critical mass concentration)
\bar{M}_n	number-average molecular weight (g·mol ⁻¹)
mol·kg ⁻¹	mole per kilogram (reactive group content)
M_{os}	Knauer pressure osmometric average molecular weight
MPa	megapascal
mS·cm ⁻¹	millisiemens per centimeter
\bar{M}_w	weight-average molecular weight
\bar{M}_v	viscosity-average molecular weight
mW·cm ⁻²	milliwatt per centimeter squared (power density)
\bar{M}_z	centrifugation-average molecular weight
MS	mass spectrometry
N	Newton
NMR	nuclear magnetic resonance
PB	poly(butadiene)
PCL	poly(caprolactone)
PDI	polydispersity index
PDMS	poly(dimethylsiloxane)
PECH	poly(epichlorohydrin)
PEI	poly(ethyleneimine)
PEO	poly(ethylene oxide)
PETA	pentaerythritol triacetate
PFPAE	perfluoropolyalkylether
PLA	poly(lactide)
POD	pin on disk
PTFE	poly(tetrafluoroethylene)
PVDMA	poly(2-vinyl-4,4-dimethylazlactone)
psi	pounds per square inch
psig	pounds per square inch gauge
Ra	average surface roughness
RGC	reactive group content
ROP	ring-opening polymerization
SANS	small angle neutron scattering
SFE	surface free energy
SLIPS	slippery liquid-infuse porous surfaces
PTMEG	polytetramethyleneglycol
SFL	stop flow lithography
TEOS	tetraethoxysilane
TFE	tetrafluoroethylene
THF	tetrahydrofuran
TOF	time-of-flight
T_c	crystallization temperature
T_d	decomposition temperature
T_f	freezing temperature
T_g	glass transition temperature
T_m	melting temperature

TMDI	trimethylhexamethylenediisocyanate
RGC	reactive group compound
SS	styrene sulfonate
UPy	uriedo-pyrimidinone
wt%	weight percent
2PP	two photon polymerization
3D	Three-dimensional

1. Introduction

Fluoropolymers [1-7], have found many applications in sophisticated technologies (high-tech) areas: in high-performance lubricants such as for magnetic recording media and as heat transfer fluids lubricants [1], elastomers [2], and pump fluids under demanding conditions. Other examples include those in the automotive industries [3] (e.g. seals, gaskets, or transmission components, fuel cells, and lithium ions batteries), aerospace and aeronautics (e.g. elastomers as gaskets or O-rings), petrochemical, microelectronics, chemical engineering (high performance membranes) [7], textile treatment, protective building coatings (e.g. paints or films resistant to UV and to graffiti), and optics (core and cladding of optical fibres) [4]. In spite of their high price (arising from the cost of the small scale fabrication and purification of the gaseous monomers), these polymers have known major developments in modern “high-tech” technologies.

Among these “high-tech” polymers, perfluoropolyalkylethers (PFPAEs) represent a special class that possesses remarkable properties (high thermal stability, excellent chemical inertness, and low surface energy that can be as low as $10\text{-}14\text{ mN}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$). They display tunable elastic modulus ($1\text{-}100\text{ MPa}$) [5,6,7] and anti-fouling characteristics [8], which make them suitable to obtain polymeric materials with high chemical resistance and extremely low wettability [9-10].

Fluorinated polyalkylethers are commercially available and, as fluorinated (co)polymers [2,10-15], these specialty macromolecules are endowed with outstanding properties, mainly linked to i) the low polarizability, strong electronegativity, and small Van der Waals radius (1.32 \AA) of the fluorine atom, and ii) the high C-F bond (the bond energy dissociation is approximately $485\text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$). In addition, the presence of oxygen bridge imparts exceptional mobility to make them amorphous [16] and thus induces very low glass transition temperatures as low as $-100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The scope of this review deals with the formation

and use of telechelic polymers where the majority of its backbone contains fluorinated alkyl ethers. This is why the PFPAE abbreviation will be used, since a few fluorinated aryl ethers exist in the literature. Many of the applications, however, utilize the polymer made from the photooxidation of perfluoroolefins normally given the trade name Fomblin®. To give a sense of their utility, the monofunctional versions of PFPAEs are liquid perfluoropolymers that display a very high gas solubility making them useful in thin films in the development of cosmetics and barrier creams that offer a very high degree of skin protection and moisture retention but still allow the skin to breathe. They can be used in high-performance lubricant applications such as for magnetic recording media [17,18] and as heat transfer fluids, even in aggressive media [2]. Further, the protection of important ancient and historical buildings where application of a monomolecular film of PFPAE to the stone surface can safeguard against the aggressive acid rain but can still allow internal absorbed water in the stone to escape as vapor [2].

Well-architected polymers based on PFPAEs have been reported as block [19,20,21], graft [22,23,24,25,26], dendrimers [27,28], etc. Telechelic (the etymology of the word from the ancient greek “télos” and “chēlē” means end term of a goal-directed process and pincer-like claw, respectively; or α,ω - difunctional) PFPAEs can be synthesized or are commercially available with functional groups such as ester, amide, amine, carboxylic acid, and iodine atoms, etc. However, this review focusses primarily on the synthesis beyond the readily available telechelic PFPAEs diol (or α,ω -dihydroxy) and various strategies to obtain well-defined fluorinated (co)polymers based on PFPAEs. **Scheme 1** provides a general overview of such intermediate PFPAE materials and their wide range of applications.

Scheme 1 : Overview of the uses of telechelic dihydroxyl PFPAs as precursors for a wide range of intermediates and well-defined fluoropolymers, including applications therefrom.

Perfluoropolyalkylethers (PFPAs) can be homopolymers or copolymers and their microstructures exhibit linear or branched conformations [29,30,31,32,33]. Lagow *et al.* [16, 34] and Chambers *et al.* [35] achieved their syntheses by direct fluorination of hydrogenated polyethers; this process requiring much care to avoid side-reactions such as cleavages of chains. Nowadays, the production of PFPAs (by direct fluorination) is developed by Exflour Research Corporation [36,37]. Commercially available PFPAs are based upon four main families: these are Fomblin[®], Krytox[®], Demnum[®], and Aflunox[®] produced by Ausimont (now Solvay Specialty Polymers), Du Pont (now Chemours), Daikin and Unimatec Companies (NOK group), respectively [1-3] (**Scheme 2**).

$\text{CF}_3(\text{OCF}_2\text{CF}_2)_p(\text{OCF}_2)_q\text{OCF}_3$	$1,000 < \bar{M}_n < 4,000$	(Fomblin [®] Z and Galden [®])
$\text{CF}_3\text{CF}_2\text{CF}_2\text{O}(\text{CF}_2\text{CF}_2\text{CF}_2\text{O})_n\text{CF}_2\text{CF}_3$	$1,600 < \bar{M}_n < 7,000$	(Demnum [®])
$\text{CF}_3\text{CF}_2\text{CF}_2[\text{OCF}_2\text{CF}(\text{CF}_3)]_n\text{F}$	$1,300 < \bar{M}_n < 10,300$	(Krytox [®])
$\text{CF}_3\text{O}[\text{CF}_2\text{CF}(\text{CF}_3)\text{O}]_p(\text{CF}_2\text{O})_n\text{CF}_3$	$600 < \bar{M}_n < 7,000$	(Fomblin [®] Y)
$\text{CF}_3(\text{OCF}_2\text{CF}_2)_p[\text{OCF}_2\text{CF}(\text{CF}_3)]_q(\text{OCF}_2)_r\text{OCF}_3$	$900 < \bar{M}_n < 10,000$	(Fomblin [®] K)

$$1,350 < \bar{M}_n < 16,600$$

(Aflunox[®] or
Aflunox[®] V)

Scheme 2. Commercially available perfluoropolyalkylethers (PFPAEs), where \bar{M}_n stands for the number-average molecular weight ($\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) of the polymer.

2. Synthesis of Telechelic Perfluoropolyalkylethers (PFPAEs) diacylfluorides

2.1 Direct Fluorination of Alkyl Ethers

Lagow, founder of Exflur Research Corporation, [38] disclosed in his patent from 1975 the formation of telechelic PFPAEs bearing carboxylic acid end-groups. The direct fluorination was conducted in a prefluorinated nickel tube reactor with incoming and outgoing lines made from copper. A tee-trap was used to scrub any of the unused fluorine upon its exit from the nickel tube reactor. Alumina was used inside the tee-trap along with a retrofitting of a nitrogen purge to prevent any oxygen or moisture from re-entering the reactor from the exit side. In one example, the methodology required the use of 0.5 grams of polyethylene oxide power grade 4,000,000 (\bar{M}_v) with a mesh size of 150. The reactor was first flushed with helium, after which fluorination at room temperature and atmospheric pressure was initiated. The flow rates of helium and fluorine during fluorination are given in Example 1 of the patent (see **Table 1**).

Table 1 : Conditions required to directly fluorinate polyethylene oxide powder in example 1 of Lagow's patent (adapted from 1975 US patent 4113772 A) [38].

He (cc/min)	F ₂ (cc/min)	Time (days)
40	0.5	1
20	1	1
10	1	1
5	1	1
0	1	1

The result of the reaction was not only replacing the hydrogen with fluorine atoms, but the ether would crack during the process to generate acyl fluorides (**Scheme 3**). Upon the addition of water, the resulting PFPAEs bear carboxylic acid end group [38].

Scheme 3 : Lagow's direct fluorination method of poly(ethylene oxide) for telechelic bis(acyl fluorides) and dicarboxylic acids (reproduced with permission from 1975 US patent 4113772) [38].

An alternative method to prepare PFPAEs from direct fluorination was demonstrated by Howell *et. al.* in 2011 [39] using alkyldiols with telechelic perfluorovinylethers provided more flexibility on the fluoroalkylether arrangement. The first step in the process provided excellent yields of tetrafluoroethylene (TFE) primary diol diadducts using a 500-mL to 1-gallon autoclaves. The reactions were initiated by KOH (60 mol%) in acetonitrile and carried out at 25 to 60 °C and 2.7 to 12.0 bar (25 to 160 psig). The diol/TFE adducts were then distilled and dehydrofluorinated with butyllithium at low temperature. For naming purposes, the bisvinylethers (BVEs) are numbered according to the glycol used in the first reaction step, for example BVE-2 is derived from ethylene glycol, BVE-3 from 1,3-propylene glycol and BVE-22 is from di(ethylene glycol). Finally, polymerization occurred in at 65–72 °C in acetonitrile and KOH producing polyfluorinated polyethers with average degrees of polymerisation (DPs) ranging from 4 to 12 in good isolated yields (80–95%). To complete the polymer, fluorination was accomplished with prolonged fluorination of diluted substrate solutions in CH₃CN with 10% fluorine/90% nitrogen at room temperature, followed by a gradual increase of temperature, substrate and fluorine concentration (**Scheme 4**).

Scheme 5: Anionic ring-opening polymerization of hexafluoropropylene oxide (HFPO) using oxalyl difluoride to produce telechelic oligo(HFPO).

2.3 Radical Photo-oxidation of Perfluoroalkenes

The photooxidation of perfluoroolefins (e.g., TFE [45], hexafluoropropylene (HFP) [46], perfluorobutadiene [47], and perfluoromethyl vinyl ether (PMVE) [48]) is the commercial option to telechelic PFPAs. This option was formerly industrialized by Montedison followed by Ausimont Company, then Solexis (now known by Solvay Specialty Polymers), yielding functional or non-functional (or neutral) Fomblin[®] oligomers. Their average molecular weights of which range from 1,000 to 4,000 g·mol⁻¹ (see **Scheme 6**) [49].

Scheme 6: Formation of telechelic PFPAs following the photooxidation of perfluoroalkene route (adopted from J Appl Polym Sci. 1996;59(2):311-327) [49].

The syntheses, properties, and applications of telechelic PFPAEs have also been reviewed by various authors several decades ago [9-12,16,50]. Since photooxidation of perfluoroalkenes is currently the dominate route to yield telechelic materials, additional attention will be given to their synthesis.

In the photooxidation process, a fluoroolefin is reacted with molecular oxygen at low temperature (typically -40 °C or lower) in the presence of ultraviolet light. The free radical peroxidic chain follows a complex mechanism and the final structure of the PFPAEs is highly dependent upon the reaction conditions [51].

Comparing the two most common fluoroolefins for production of PFPAEs, HFP and TFE, the photooxidation of HFP is conducted in bulk monomer due to its inherently low reactivity. HFP does not propagate even under radical polymerization [51]. Liquid-phase photooxidation of HFP has been well studied [52], resulting in the development of a kinetic model describing the relative importance of the elementary reactions occurring during the process. The polymerization begins after a short induction period where minute quantities of HFP are converted to CF_3COF and peroxides. Photolysis of these compounds generates radical species and initiates the photo-oxidation process. Bunyard *et al.* [53] supplied a comprehensive mechanism that contributes to chain propagation and termination as well as the evolution of the average molecular weights versus the HFP concentration, varying from 900 to 2800 $\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ (**Figure 1**).

Fig. 1. Hexafluoropropylene oxide repeat unit (C₃) content as a function of HFP versus concentration in (●) carbon dioxide, (■) bulk HFP, and (▲) PCB at -40 °C [53]. Copyright 1999, Reproduced with permission from ACS Publications.

The photooxidation of TFE is a complex and hazardous reaction (**Scheme 6**). Solvay Specialty Polymers has succeeded in safely handling and manipulating the starting materials for a successful manufacturing process. Their introductory work leads to telechelic PFPAE diesters which are reduced to diols, marketed under the ZDEAL[®] and ZDOL[®] tradenames, respectively (**Scheme 6**). However, to be successful, an inert diluent for TFE or HFP photooxidations is required in order to prevent homopolymerization of the specific fluoroolefin. Historically, dichlorodifluoromethane was the preferred solvent, but the use of other low boiling perfluoroalkanes has also been reported [54]. Turri *et al.* [55] studied the chain transfer of chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) for fluoroolefin photooxidation reactions. Since, CFCs were commercially phased out, other solvents had to be explored. For example, Bunyard *et al.* [53] discovered that the HFP photooxidation synthesis could be carried out in varying HFP concentrations (3.7-8.8 M) in carbon dioxide, paralleling reactions which were conducted in bulk HFP and perfluorocyclobutane. The photooxidation production using carbon dioxide was conducted in a high-pressure reactor [53] modified for use at low temperature and UV irradiation. The reactions were irradiated under an oxygen head pressure of ca. 2 bar for 15 h at -40 °C. All reactions were homogeneous throughout the irradiation period and produced

white liquids with isolated yields ranging from 16 to 48%. The authors believed the design of the reactor precluded efficient irradiation to reach much higher yields. As reported in section 4, various authors clearly characterized these oligomers by ^{19}F NMR spectroscopy or mass spectroscopy to supply the polymer composition, number-average molecular weight (\bar{M}_n), and peroxide content [56,57,58].

3. Commercially Available Telechelic PFPAEs

Functionalized PFPAEs have been reported by various groups [2,17,50,59]. Figure 3 lists some of the most common commercially available oligomers marketed by Solvay Specialty Polymers, Exflur Research Corporation, and Shin Etsu Chemical Company, discussed in the review:

X-CF₂(OCF₂)_m(OCF₂CF₂)_nOCF₂-X with

X: C(O)OH

Fomblin® Z DIAC or Fluorolink C

X: C(O)OCH₃

Fomblin® Z-DEAL or Fluorolink L

X: C(O)NHC₁₈H₃₇

Fluorolink® A10P

X: CH₂OH

Fomblin® Z-DOL 2000,2500,4000 or Fluorolink® D

X: CH₂OP(O)(OH)₂

Fluorolink® F10

Fluorolink® S10

X : CH₂(OCH₂CH₂)_pOH

Fomblin® Z DOL TX or Fluorolink E10H

X : CH₂OCH₂CH(OH)CH₂OH

Fomblin® Z TETRAOL or Fluorolink T

Fomblin® AM 2001 or 3001

Fomblin® MD40 or MD 700

Fomblin® AD1700

X-CF₂(OCF₂CF₂)_nOCF₂-X with

X : COOCH₃

C6GDIMEST, C8GDIMEST

X : Br

C6GDIBR,

X :CH₂OH

C6GDIOL, C8GDIOL

X :C(O)F

C6GDIACF, C8GDIACF

X : C(O)OH

C6GDIAC, C8GDIAC

X-CF(CF₃)[OCF₂CF(CF₃)]_m(OCF₂CF₂O)[CF(CF₃)CF₂O]_nCF(CF₃)-X with

Fig. 2. Examples of commercially available telechelic PFPAs produced by Solvay Specialty Polymers, Exflur Research Corporation, and Shin Etsu Chemical Company (where ~~~ represents the connection to the PFPAs chain).

These difunctional polymers listed above are usually insoluble in common organic solvents and are in some cases prone to undergo additional reactions. Typically, the number of steps to generate the desired functional group is one, up to two or three synthetic steps at the most. For example, the carboxylic acid and the methyl ester are formed from the acyl fluoride, by adding water or methanol, respectively. The methylene alcohol is prepared by reducing the methyl ester using LiAlH₄ (LAH) or NaBH₄. The Z-DOL TX is achieved by mixing the alkoxide of the methylene alcohol with ethylene oxide [60] while the Z-TETRAOL is formed by reacting the alkoxide of the methylene alcohol with glycidol [17]. Fomblin® AM is produced from the addition of the alkoxide onto 5-(bromomethyl)-1,3-benzodioxole [61]. In addition, Fomblin® MD40 is a urethane methacrylate [62] obtained by reacting 2-methacryloyloxyethyl isocyanate with either Fluorolink®D10 H or Fluorolink®E10 H to yield the corresponding Fomblin AM 2001 or AM 3001, respectively. C6GDIBR from Exflur Research Corp., can be achieved by the decarbonylation of the acylbromide. The acylbromide is derived from the carboxylic acid using thionylbromide (**Scheme 2**). Shin Etsu SIFEL® Liquid F-Elastomer can be formed by the condensation reaction of the methylester with the desired amine (e.g. NH(CH₃)Ph-Si(CH₃)₂-CH=CH₂) or an S_N2 reaction of the alcohol to a given allyl halide followed by hydrosilylation. The other SIFEL® elastomers, as an example, can be created by converting the acyl iodide to the iodide via decarbonylation, adding ethylene, dehydroiodinate, then followed by the hydrosilylation of the newly formed alkene with the target HSi(CH₃)₂CH=CH₂ to create SIFEL® X-71 8115 [63] (see **Scheme 34** in section 6.3.3).

4. Characterization and Properties of PFPAs

There is little information in the literature on the characterization of telechelic PFPAs. Therefore, the characterization of monofunctional versions of the PFPAs will be reported to

allow the readers interested in exploring such a chemistry to infer the information onto the telechelic PFPAEs.

4.1 Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) Spectroscopy

Karis's [58] (**Table 2**), and Turri's [64] research groups reported considerable ^{19}F NMR characterizations on the most common PFPAEs. Ciampelli et al. [57] supplied ^{19}F chemical shifts of carbon fluorine moieties near oxygens. More recently, Lopez *et al.* [65] published ^{19}F NMR spectra of Fomblin® Z-DOL (**Figure 3**). The majority of the work was on Solvay Specialty Polymer's materials (Fomblin®), although DuPont's and Daikin's products were analyzed by Karis's group as well. Peak assignments for ^{19}F NMR chemical shifts of commercially available PFPAEs are listed in Tables 2 and 3 and include both the end groups and internal units. In addition, Hill and Erdman [40] did considerable work on the calculating the number average molecular weight of difunctional materials containing HFPO units. Overall, procedures for calculating the PFPAE's number average molecular weights and degrees of polymerization and/or compositions of the polymers by NMR spectroscopy were reviewed by all three of the above research groups.

Table 2 : ^{19}F -NMR chemical shifts of Fomblin®Z-type PFPAE end-groups (Adapted from J Fluorine Chem. 2002;118 :81–94) [58].

The spectrometer was set to a spectral width of 20,000– 40,000 Hz, a 458 pulse width of 25 ms, 256 scans, and a relaxation delay of 0.5 s. The samples were held in 5 mm NMR tubes neat. It is surmised that the reference was hexafluorobenzene.

Z03	$\begin{array}{c} -57.6 \\ \downarrow \\ \text{—OCF}_2\text{OCF}_3 \end{array}$	$\begin{array}{c} -55.6 \\ \downarrow \\ \text{—OCF}_2\text{CF}_2\text{OCF}_3 \end{array}$
Zdol	$\begin{array}{c} -80.7 \\ \downarrow \\ \text{—OCF}_2\text{OCF}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH} \end{array}$	$\begin{array}{c} -82.7 \\ \downarrow \\ \text{—OCF}_2\text{CF}_2\text{OCF}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH} \end{array}$
Zdiac	$\begin{array}{c} -77.0 \\ \downarrow \\ \text{—OCF}_2\text{OCF}_2\text{COOCH} \end{array}$	$\begin{array}{c} -79.0 \\ \downarrow \\ \text{—OCF}_2\text{CF}_2\text{OCF}_2\text{COOH} \end{array}$
Zdeal	$\begin{array}{c} -77.5 \\ \downarrow \\ \text{—OCF}_2\text{OCF}_2\text{COOCH}_3 \end{array}$	$\begin{array}{c} -79.2 \\ \downarrow \\ \text{—OCF}_2\text{CF}_2\text{OCF}_2\text{COOCH}_3 \end{array}$
Zetraol	$\begin{array}{c} -77.5 \\ \downarrow \\ \text{—OCF}_2\text{OCF}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{CH}_2\text{OH} \end{array}$	$\begin{array}{c} -79.7 \\ \downarrow \\ \text{—OCF}_2\text{CF}_2\text{OCF}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{CH}_2\text{OH} \end{array}$
ZdolTX	$\begin{array}{c} -77.3 \\ \downarrow \\ \text{—OCF}_2\text{OCF}_2\text{CH}_2(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2)_{1.5}\text{OH} \end{array}$	$\begin{array}{c} -79.4 \\ \downarrow \\ \text{—OCF}_2\text{CF}_2\text{OCF}_2\text{CH}_2(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2)_{1.5}\text{OH} \end{array}$

¹⁹F-NMR chemical shifts of Demnum®- and Krytox®-type PFAE end-groups

¹⁹F-chemical shifts of Fomblin® Z, Demnum®, Krytox® - type PFAE internal unit

Fig. 3. ¹⁹F-NMR spectrum (CD₃OD) of poly(tetrafluoroethylene oxide-co-difluoromethylene oxide)- α,ω -diol (Fomblin® Z-DOL) [65]. Copyright 2016, Reproduced with permission from Royal Society of Chemistry.

Rinaldi *et al.* [66] spent great effort in understanding PFPAs based upon monofunctional oligo(HFPO). They used multiple two-dimensional nuclear magnetic resonance (2D-NMR) techniques to characterize the structures of Krytox[®] using a model compound containing four HFPO units (K4) (**Scheme 7**). They specifically reported coupling constants (J) for fluorine as well as chemical shifts of fluorine and carbon within the molecule (**Table 3**). Selective, ¹⁹F-¹⁹F COSY 2D-NMR experiments were performed with different excitation regions for more simplified spectra.

Scheme 7 : oligo(HFPO) or K4 and its labeled CF_x units for Table 3.

Table 3 : ¹⁹F- and ¹³C- NMR chemical shift assignments for each CF_x unit and the related ⁿJ_{FF} coupling in each of the four (I-IV) distinguishable stereoisomers. (adapted from Magn Reson Chem. 2011;49:413–424) [66].

Group	Chemical Shift ^a J-Coupling	Isomer			
		I	II	III	IV
A ₂	δ ¹⁹ F	-81.83 ² J _{FF} =151±5Hz ⁴ J _{FF} =25±5Hz	-81.88 ² J _{FF} =155±5Hz ⁴ J _{FF} =25±5Hz	-81.90 ² J _{FF} =157±5Hz ⁴ J _{FF} =25±5Hz	-81.79 ² J _{FF} =148±5Hz ⁴ J _{FF} =25±5Hz
	δ ¹³ C	116.93	116.93	116.93	116.93
a ₂	δ ¹⁹ F	-130.18	-130.20	-130.20	-130.22
	δ ¹³ C	108.01	108.01	108.01	108.01
A ₃	δ ¹⁹ F	-82.41	-82.41	-82.41	-82.41
	δ ¹³ C	118.47	118.47	118.47	118.47
B ₁	δ ¹⁹ F	-144.68 ³ J _{FF} =44±5Hz	-144.84 ³ J _{FF} =44±5Hz	-144.88 ³ J _{FF} =44±5Hz	-144.59 ³ J _{FF} =44±5Hz
	δ ¹³ C	104.13	104.13	104.13	104.13
B ₂	δ ¹⁹ F	-80.21 ² J _{FF} =130±5Hz ⁴ J _{FF} =25±5Hz	-80.34 ² J _{FF} =150±5Hz ⁴ J _{FF} =25±5Hz	-80.34 ² J _{FF} =140±5Hz ⁴ J _{FF} =25±5Hz	-80.41 ² J _{FF} =146±5Hz ⁴ J _{FF} =25±5Hz
	δ ¹³ C	117.44	117.44	117.44	117.44
B ₃	δ ¹⁹ F	-80.73	-80.73	-80.73	-80.73
	δ ¹³ C	118.94	118.94	118.94	118.94
C _{2a}	δ ¹⁹ F	-78.86 ² J _{FF} =150±5Hz ⁴ J _{FF} =25±5Hz	-78.91 ² J _{FF} =150±5Hz ⁴ J _{FF} =25±5Hz	-78.91 ² J _{FF} =150±5Hz ⁴ J _{FF} =25±5Hz	-78.72 ² J _{FF} =150±5Hz ⁴ J _{FF} =25±5Hz
	δ ¹³ C	117.80	117.80	117.80	117.81

C _{2b}	$\delta^{19}\text{F}$	-84.99 ² J _{FF} =150±5Hz ⁴ J _{FF} =25±5Hz	-84.76 ² J _{FF} =150±5Hz ⁴ J _{FF} =25±5Hz	-84.69 ² J _{FF} =150±5Hz ⁴ J _{FF} =25±5Hz	-85.06 ² J _{FF} =150±5Hz ⁴ J _{FF} =25±5Hz
	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$	117.80	117.80	117.80	117.81
C ₃	$\delta^{19}\text{F}$	-80.73	-80.73	-80.73	-80.73
	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$	118.94	118.94	118.94	118.94
Z ₁	$\delta^{19}\text{F}$	-132.41 ³ J _{FF} =21±5Hz	-132.41 ³ J _{FF} =21±5Hz	-132.42 ³ J _{FF} =21±5Hz	-132.49 ³ J _{FF} =21±5Hz
	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$	101.86	101.86	101.86	101.86
Z ₃	$\delta^{19}\text{F}$	-83.33	-83.33	-83.37	-83.37
	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$	119.23	119.23	119.22	119.22

^a Chemical shifts are accurate to ±0.01 ppm; ¹⁹F NMR shifts were measured from 1D ¹⁹F and 2D exclusive COSY spectra; ¹³C NMR shifts were determined from ¹J_{CF}-HSQC spectra.

To our knowledge, Howell *et al.* [67] was the first group to report the carbon-fluorine coupling constants of oligo(HFPO), with its different end-groups, while no ¹³C NMR spectrum of telechelic PFPAEs has been reported.

Scheme 8 : oligo(HFPO) used in Table 4 for end-group chemical shifts and coupling values.

Table 4 : ¹³C NMR spectral data of ethyl-F [X =F], hydrogen end-cap (HEC) [X =H], and isopropyl alkoxide-F (IPA-F) [X=CF₃] poly-HFPO (adapted from J Fluorine Chem. 1998;89(1) :131-135) [67].

	C(4)	C(5)
<i>Ethyl</i> (<i>n</i> =4, <i>X</i> =F)		
δ [ppm]	117.9 (tq)	115.6 (qt)
¹ J[Hz]	283.7	286.5
² J [Hz]	40.6	44.4
<i>HEC</i> (<i>n</i> =4, <i>X</i> =H)		
δ [ppm]	97.85 (ddqt)	119 (qd)
¹ J[Hz]	244.8/181.9	279.7
² J [Hz]	42.9	31.1
³ J [Hz]	5.3	
<i>IPA</i> (<i>n</i> =5, <i>X</i> =CF ₃)		
δ [ppm]	103.6 (dsept)	119.2 (qd)
¹ J[Hz]	268.3	287.0
² J[Hz]	39.1	30.8

4.2 Mass Spectrometry

Several groups have characterized various PFPAE functional materials by mass spectrometry. De Voogt's team [68] analyzed a telechelic phosphate PFPAE (**Scheme 9**) using two types of spectrometers. The first one was maXis 4G QTOF (QqTOF) (Bruker Daltonics, Germany) for the preliminary survey of the PFPAE formulation. The second spectrometer was an Orbitrap VelosPro, Hybrid Linear Ion Trap/Orbitrap MS (Thermo Scientific, USA). The orbitrap was used to study the mass defects and the fragmentation of the polymer.

Scheme 9 : telechelic bis(phosphonic acid) PFPAEs made from Fomblin® z DOL TX (adapted from J Am Soc Mass Spectrom. 2016;27:309–318) [68].

Saprygin *et al.* [69] used gas chromatography and chemical ionization with isobutylene for the determination of PFPAE concentrations, while Howell *et al.* [67] identified the end-groups by means of GC/EIMS. From Matrix Laser Desorption Ionization-Time-of-Flight Mass analysis (MALDI-TOF-MS) Kudo *et al.* [70] characterized PFPAEs on hard disk storage devices. In addition, Spool and Kasai [71] demonstrated that a negative ion TOF-SIMS study of PFPAEs was extremely sensitive and a useful route to elucidate structural features of parent PFPAE chains. Finally, Kostjuk *et al.* [72] and Lapčik *et al.* [21] demonstrated and expanded the use of MALDI-TOF-MS (Ultraflex spectrometer or Bruker Ultraflex III by Bruker Daltonik, Germany). These systems were very useful in identifying the average molecular weights and polydispersities of PFPAEs based upon oligo(HFPO)-*b*-PEO diblock copolymers [21]. Positive ionization methods were useful if the PFPAE had a high organic content in its functionalization while negative ionization methods were more useful for very high fluorine content with little in way of hydrocarbon content. Sample preparation utilized LiCl and *trans*-2-[3-(4-*tert*-butylphenyl)-2-methyl-2-propenylidene]malononitrile (DCTB) or perfluorocinnamic acid as a matrix with PFPAEs. For PFPAE acylfluoride analysis, normally the acylfluoride is first converted to the methyl ester and then followed by a condensation reaction with diethylamine [73]. The amide reduces the volatility of the PFPAE for analysis (**Figure 4**).

Fig. 4. Indirect method for analyzing PFPAC acylfluoride, by conversion to a lower volatile amide. By Matrix assisted laser desorption ionization-time-of-flight mass spectrum (MALDI-TOF-MS) [73]. Copyright 2014, Reproduced with permission from Division of Polymer Chemistry, Inc.

4.3 Chemical, Physical and Thermal Properties

Several authors have studied the chemical, physical, and thermal properties of PFPACs. Sianesi *et al.* [74] investigated the viscosities of various PFPACs and their behavior in oxygen at high pressure and high temperature. The density of PFPACs is about twice that of mineral oils (**Table 5**). They display a viscosity index comparable to mineral oils and better than other commercially available fluorinated fluids. Preserving the liquid state over a wide range of temperatures is very important technologically [75]. PFPACs are insoluble in most organic and inorganic solvents except fluorinated types (e.g. Freon[®] 11, Freon[®] 113, Vertrel[™] XF, Novec[™] Engineered Fluid HFE-7000 or HFE-7100, Solkane[®]365 mfc, etc.) which makes them useful for lubrication in the presence of gasoline or petroleum derivatives and solvents commonly used in the chemical industry. PFPAC fluids are inflammable and practically have no flash-point.

4.3.1 Chemical Properties

PFPACs exhibit outstanding thermal stability since they preserve their properties at low and high temperatures. In addition, they are inert to aggressive chemicals such as inorganic and organic bases and acids, halogens and oxidizers [76]. They are compatible with

missile fuels and oxidizers such as hydrocarbon fuel, diethylenetriamine, unsymmetrical dimethylhydrazine, hydrogen peroxide, liquid oxygen, and inhibited red fuming nitric acid. Lewis acids such as aluminum trichloride and antimony pentafluoride are the only reactants that enable the decomposition of such fluids at 100 °C [76].

Furthermore, the resistance to oxidizing materials and particularly to oxygen and fluorine is the most outstanding property of PFPAEs. They have been used in liquid oxygen systems and in the presence of oxygen at high temperature and pressure [77]. Determination of ignition temperature and impact tests [78] enabled the determination of the maximum operating conditions of PFPAE fluids in oxygen handling equipment. The ignition temperatures are very close to the threshold of the thermal decomposition in inert atmosphere, which means that the initial ignition reaction is the thermal homolysis of the polymer chain. PFPAEs were tested up to ignition. The stability toward oxygen depends on the molecular weight and fluid type. For example, Y/R regarded as the least stable, has an allowable maximum oxygen pressure of 91 bar at 250 °C.

4.3.2 Thermal Properties

During thermal degradation no tar and sludges are formed. The dynamic thermogravimetric pattern of PFPAEs compared with that of PTFE were compared by isothermal analysis [74]. The authors studied the weight loss rates under inert atmosphere and in oxygen, for the fluid of high average molecular weight. The temperature for the PFPAEs is strongly dependent on the chemical stabilization of the terminal end groups and marginally on the molecular weight of the oligomers.

In the absence of metals, the degradation mechanism of PFPAEs is of the free radical type. The initiation reaction is followed by a beta scission propagation step. For PFPAEs, the C-C bond in the chain is the weakest one and, when broken, the whole macromolecule decomposes with evolution of gaseous products such as C_3F_6 , CF_3COF , and COF_2 .

Furthermore, Sianesi *et al.* [74] showed that at temperatures higher than 300 °C, the inertness of PFPAEs is strongly affected by the presence of some metals. Moreover, certain Al or Ti alloys induce fluid degradation at 250 °C. The degradation involves an oxidized surface on the metals. By X-ray analysis, the presence of Al_2O_3 and TiO_2 was found

on the surface of some alloys of Al or Ti after thermal treatment. The effect of inorganic oxides on the degradation of Y/R type PFPAE is shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Effect of oxides onto the stability of PFPAEs: isotherms by TGA in air at 360 °C [74]. Copyright 1971, Reproduced with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd.

However, the effect of metals on the fluids can be prevented by the use of stabilizers. At a well-defined temperature, related to the testing conditions, rapid degradation of the unstabilized fluid occurs. This temperature varies with PFPAE structure and is also dependant to a lesser extent on the specific surface value of Al₂O₃, powder and other morphological properties. Alumina, upon heating, induces vacant sites on the surface [79] and these sites may coordinate the C-O bond in PFPAEs being able to strongly reduce the activation energy for the breaking of the ether bond and the subsequent unzipping of the chain. The gaseous products of decomposition are toxic and corrosive in the presence of humidity.

The topochemical mechanism of decomposition, catalyzed by these oxides, is also supported by the inhibitory effect on degradation of some organic nitrogen bases or

certain Lewis bases. The Lewis acid nature of Al_2O_3 can be measured by stoichiometric titration with nitrogen bases such as pyridine or quinolone [80].

Several different classes of stabilizers with a strong inhibition on Al_2O_3 are also effective with metals in the micro-oxidation test [74]. The high number of physically equivalent conformers in PFPAEs inhibits crystallization at very low temperature. The only physical transition shown at low temperature is the glass transition temperature (T_g) which for oligomers and low molecular weight polymers depends on the chain length [81]. The freezing temperatures (i.e., pour points) of the different cuts of PFPAEs are correlated with their molecular weights and their T_g s reported by Sianesi *et al.* [74].

4.3.3 Conclusion

PFPAEs display quite interesting chemical, physical and thermal properties at low and high temperatures. Such properties as well as viscoelastic properties are assigned to the high flexibility of the polymer chain due to the carbon-oxygen bonds. Such a high flexibility prevents them from crystallizing and explains their low T_g , hence, providing a large temperature range of liquid state with a good viscosity index. The influence of metals on the thermal stability of these fluids has been explained by a topochemical reaction mechanism and a technique based on this mechanism has been developed for testing unstabilized fluids and for screening of the stabilizers. The high stability and good antiwear properties make PFPAE fluids and greases suitable lubricants for long-life in hostile environments.

4.4 Rheology

This section lists the literature regarding the glass transition temperature, density, expansion coefficient, and viscosity of PFPAEs. Karis and Jhon [82] reported the relationship of tribological properties of PFPAEs that takes into account their viscosity, molecular structure, degree of polymerization, and temperature. A sudden increase in the friction coefficient was determined using the pin on disk (POD) test where the PFPAE was incrementally removed from the track with each sliding cycle [82]. The increase in friction determined the failure rate of the PFPAE. Molecular theory for polymer melt rheology was employed to develop a universal scaling rule.

Sianesi *et al.* [51,74] and Falcone [83] described several chemical and physical properties of the Fomblin® Y series while Ouano *et al.* [84] reported the density and viscosity of several Krytox® homopolymers. However, Marchionni *et al.* [85] determined the T_g , the

viscosities, and various molecular weights for two different series of PFPAEs. One PFPAE was branched (Y) whereas the others were linear (Z). The chemical and physical properties are given in

Table 5 and the molecular weights of the PFPAEs in

Table 6.

Table 5 : Chemical and physical properties of PFPAEs (Fomblin® Y and Z ; structures are given in Scheme 2 and Figure 2) (adapted from Eur Poly J. 1988 ;24(12):1211-1216) [85].

Sample	M_{os}	T_g (K)	ρ (293) (g·cm ⁻³)	$\alpha \times 10^{-3}$ (°C ⁻¹)	η (293) (mPa · sec)
Y1	753	142	1.784	1.2513	3.5
Y2	1109	174	1.857	1.0078	31.3
Y3	1199	182	1.866	0.9719	48.7
Y4	1801	188	1.881	0.9595	115.7
Y5	2467	196	1.892	0.9385	249.6
Y6	3260	195	1.898	0.8850	498.6
Y7	6530	208	1.913	0.8563	2806.0
Z1	1800	134	1.721	1.4504	2.5
Z2	3581	137.1	1.8288	0.9673	53.4
Z3	7087	140.3	1.8372	1.0383	280.2
Z4	9684	141.7	1.8445	1.0064	432.0
Z5	11,892	140.8	1.848	0.9942	1096.0

Note : average molecular weights were determined by using a Knauer Vapour Pressure Osmometer (M_{os}), Glass transition (T_g), density (ρ), free volume expansion coefficients (α), viscosity (η)

Table 6 : Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC) data of Frombin® Y and Z (adapted from Eur Poly J. 1988 ;24(12) :1211-1216) [85].

Sample	\bar{M}_n	\bar{M}_w	\bar{M}_z	\bar{M}_w/\bar{M}_n
Y1	653	682	710	1.044
Y2	1319	1365	1415	1.035
Y4	1944	2010	2085	1.034
Y5	2432	2535	2640	1.042
Y6	3078	3355	3670	1.090
Y7	5104	5600	5980	1.097
Z2	2520	5080	-----	2.01
Z3	6440	10,700	-----	1.66
Z4	10,100	12,800	-----	1.27
Z5	12,400	17,700	-----	1.34

Regarding the trends found in the two different Fomblin® based materials, T_g increases with molecular weight and branching of the PFPAE (**Figure 6**). Fomblin® Y which is branched has a higher T_g (216.5 K) and is not far from that determined by the Gibbs-Di Marzio equation, whereas Fomblin® Z has a lower T_g (142.1 K).

Fig. 6. Dependence of T_g on average molecular weight (M_n , $\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) for PFPAEs. Continuous line from least-squares fitting; dashed line calculated from Gibbs-Di Marzio equation, ● Y; ■ Z, [85]. Copyright 1988, Reproduced with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd

Sianesi *et al.* [74] also obtained a series of PFPAE fractions of narrow molecular weight distribution, the T_g and freezing temperatures were related to the average molecular weight of the fractions (**Figure 7**) and this relationship can be rationalized by eqn. (A) [81].

$$T_g = T_g(\infty) - \frac{K}{M} \quad \text{equation (A)}$$

Figure 7 : Average molecular weights ($\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) versus glass transition temperature (T_g) and freezing temperature (T_f) of PFPAEs fractions [74]. Copyright 1971, Reproduced with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd.

The small influence of average molecular weight distribution on T_g enabled the calculations of T_g or T_f from the viscosity. A similar relationship, eqn. (B) with the average molecular weight was found with the freezing temperature determined according to the ASTM D97/57 method.

$$T_f = T_f^o(\infty) - \frac{K}{M} \quad \text{equation (B)}$$

The authors demonstrated that the data fit well for a K' value of 8.5×10^4 for average molecular weights ranging between 10^3 and 10^4 . The magnitude of bulk (volume) viscosity at the glass transition temperature for oligomeric and polymeric compounds varies according to literature [86], in the range of 10^{12} - 10^{13} poise [79].

As for density, in general, branched PFPAEs produced from the photooxidation of HFP exhibit a higher density than linear PFPAEs synthesized from TFE (**Figure 8**).

Fig. 8. Density dependence on temperature for Fomblin® Y and Z PFPAEs. □ Z1; ⊕Z2; ⊙Z3; ⊖Z4; ⊗Z5; ▲Y1; △Y2; □Y3; ▽Y4; ●Y5; ■Y6; ▼Y7, [85]. Copyright 1988, Reproduced with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd.

Figure 9 represents the shear viscosity versus the average molecular weights of Fomblin® Y and Z. It is noted that the slope changes very little for the linear PFPAE Z whether it is at -20 or 100 °C, but the slope changes more dramatically for the branched PFPAE Y.

Since the slopes of the log-log curves (Figure 10) are seen to be independent of temperature, this figure provides evidence that the friction coefficient varies with temperature uniformly for the sample [85]. The "critical" molecular weight (M_c) related to the chain length between entanglements value for this PFPAE Y cannot be straightforwardly determined. It can be tentatively located at values equal or higher than 5,000-6,000 g·mol⁻¹. Data for PFPAE Z, obtained over a wider range of molecular weight, show that M_c lies at about 7,800 g·mol⁻¹.

Fig. 9. Relationship between zero shear viscosity and M_w for Y and Z PFPAs measured at various temperatures: \blacktriangle -20°C ; \bullet 100°C [85]. Copyright 1988, Reproduced with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd.

Fig. 10. Left) Dependence of the zero shear viscosity on the reduced temperature ($T - T_g$) for Y and Z PFPAs. Symbols \square Z1; \oplus Z2; \circ Z3; \ominus Z4; \otimes Z5; \blacktriangle Y1; \triangle Y2; \square Y3; ∇ Y4; \bullet Y5; \blacksquare Y6; \blacktriangledown Y7; Right) Relationship between zero shear viscosity and M_w for Y perfluoropolyalkylethers

measured at constant ($T - T_g$) i.e. at constant frictional coefficient [85]. Copyright 1988, Reproduced with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd.

4.5 Lubricity

PFPAEs are regarded as excellent lubricants [1-2] (see section 7.1). To understand their lubricity, Howell *et al.* [39] reported a type of viscosity index, using a semi-log plot (Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata. **11**). It is linear in the y-axis [viscosity ratio (40 °C/100 °C)] and logarithmic in the x-axis for viscosities at 40 °C for various average molecular weights of the same PFPAEs. They determined flow behaviour of different PFPAEs at various temperatures, whether they were the same or different molecular weights. Of the PFPAE tested, Fomblin® Z had the lowest change of its viscosity over 100 °C temperature range. Actually, for better lubricity in cold climates, a PFPAE with little branching and more ether linkages in the structure is less viscous providing better lubricity, such as cold-crank case lubrication applications. Also, lubricity will be better in high temperature applications where branching exists in the PFPAE molecules, proving to be a thin film of protection. Surprisingly, the newly formed 2,2,2,3 polymer, $[-(\text{CF}_2\text{CF}_2\text{O})_3(\text{CF}_2\text{CF}_2\text{CF}_2\text{O})_1-]$, did not display a better viscosity index. Cross-linking during direct fluorination was suggested as the rationale for the negative influence on viscosity.

Figure 11 : Viscosity index of various PFPAEs. Y-axis viscosity of given PFPAE at 40 °C divided by the Viscosity at 100 °C. X-axis is the \log_{10} of the viscosity at 40 °C for various average molecular weights of the same PFPAEs [39]. Copyright 2011, Reproduced with permission from John Wiley & Sons Ltd.

In the same body of work, viscosity at 40 °C was reported (Table 7) along with viscosities for all the newly formed PFPAEs.

Table 7 : Selected viscosities of commercially available PFPAEs (adapted from Lubrication Science. 2011;23:61–80) [39].

PFPAE types	Viscosity, at 40 °C [cSt]
Demnum® S20	21
Demnum® S65	64
Demnum® S100	102
Fomblin® Z15	92
Krytox® GPL 103	30
Krytox® GPL 104	60
Krytox® GPL 105	160

4.6 Chromatography

In addition, a few studies have been reported on the determination of the molecular weights or separations of PFPAEs. In the realm of liquid chromatography, one study used GPC [Errore. Il segnalibro non è definito.] with a ternary solvent system, column packing, and a detector (refractive index) optimized to perform high resolution GPC on Fomblin®Zdol. The solvents used for the mobile phase are given in Table 8.

Table 8 : Physical properties and optical constants of the GPC solvent (adapted from the J Fluorine Chem. 2002;118:81–94) [56].

Component	Reference	Refractive Index	Molecular Weight (g·mol ⁻¹)	Density (Kg·m ⁻³)	Molar volume, V _i (m ³ ·mol ⁻¹)	Molar refraction, R _i (m ³ ·mol ⁻¹)
Vertrel® XF	*	1.30000	252.06	1600.0	15.7500E-5	2.9450E-5
Acetonitrile	**	1.34423	41.05	785.7	5.2250E-5	1.1075E-5
Methanol	**	1.32288	32.04	791.4	4.0485E-5	0.8232E-5

*DuPont Vertrel Data Sheet** R.C. Weast, Handbook of Chemistry and Physics, 56th ed., CRC Press, Ohio, 1975. Vertrel® XF (CF₃CF₂CFHCFHCF₃)

Tonelli *et al.* [87] also studied the isothermal equilibrium of PFPAEs on a silica packed column for separations using bis(trifluoromethyl)benzene/isopropanol (80:20 v v⁻¹) as the mobile phase. They found that the occupied area of each single PFPAE molecule increases proportionally to the average molecular weight, which fits with a classic theoretical approach. Also, the PFPAEs affinity toward the silica parallels the number of functional groups thus making it feasible to separate monofunctional from telechelic PFPAE diols.

Valsecchi *et al.* [88] and Nielsen *et al.* [89] demonstrated that supercritical CO₂ as the mobile phase can be an effective method for the fractionation of a polydisperse mixture of telechelic diol PFPAE oligomers which have an average molecular weight greater than 1100 g·mol⁻¹. Howell *et. al* [67] is the only group that reported the use of gas chromatography (GC) in conjunction with thermal conditions to separate different functional groups of similar chain length.

4.7 PFPAEs: Health and the Environment

There is minimal discussion on the long-term effects of PFPAEs in the environment [90] and what impact this class of polymer would have on society. Currently, the US FDA lists PFPAEs as an additive that can be used in materials intended for contact with food [91,92]. There has also been an extensive study achieved regarding Fomblin® based PFPAEs [93] for dermal toxicity, acute toxicity, inhalation toxicity, and oral toxicity. The report showed inactivity of the PFPAE in the rat even after repeated high-dose ingestion of

PFPAE. The apparent absence of Fomblin® HC absorption from the gastrointestinal tract in this rat study suggests that dermal absorption in humans will be minimal [93]. It is also known that intake via food happens only for molecules having sizes able to pass through the human intestinal barrier, corresponding to an average molecular weight lower than 1000 g·mol⁻¹, i.e., a ~C70 linear, hydrogenated, alkyl chain. As fluorine is 19 times heavier than hydrogen, it is only considered relevant to monitor fluorochemicals weighing up to 3600 g·mol⁻¹. Among the fluoropolymers, those containing PFPAEs are non-bioaccumulative and non-toxic referenced [94]. They suggest that PFPAEs avoid the safety, environmental and health concerns of conventional long perfluoroalkyl-chain chemistries, without sacrificing key performance features. The safety of these materials are also clearly reported by the Environment and Climate Change Canada [94]. In addition, it was demonstrated by Janjic *et al.* [95] that PFPAE can be used for medical ¹⁹F-magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) in animals with no ill effects and that PFPAE derivatives made to stabilize the nanoemulsion is also not toxic to cells. In other reports by Jellali *et al.* [62], PFPAE was investigated for biomaterial applications, especially in cell culture and tissue engineering. When microstructured PFPAE was found to promote the formation of a 3D cell layer, this finding indicated that PFPAE polymers have a potential for use in the development of biomaterials and also indicates the toxicity to humans is minimal.

Finally, when considering PFPAEs, recycling of the materials is also essential [96]. Several companies currently recycle PFPAE derivatives (e.g. Chemours, UMEX GmbH, etc.). Other options could be high temperature combustion of the polymer for small fluorinated building blocks or complete destruction of it to form the mineral fluorospar (CaF₂) (**Fig. 12**).

Fig. 12. Fluoropolymer recycling loop [96]. Copyright 2016, Reproduced with permission from Royal Society of Chemistry.

4.8 Conclusion

In addition to exceptional properties of these PFPAEs (chemical, thermal, and tribological), the intent of the characterization section is to provide helpful guidance in PFPAE properties and in the future preparation of telechelic materials for new applications. It is worth noting that the literature seems to communicate that these PFPAE materials are low risk for toxicity and bioaccumulation. In addition, it is a good reminder that PFPAE recycling, not unlike other polymers, must always be considered when being wise in the use of all resources and when servicing new societal needs.

5. Intermediate Telechelic PFPAEs for Materials

Besides bis(hydroxyl) telechelic or bis(carboxylic acid) PFPAEs which are by far the most known and produced, although Shin Etsu markets an elastomer registered as Sifel[®], the end groups of PFPAEs can also be iodides [97,98,99], alkyl carboxylates [17, 100, 101], phosphonic acids and esters [59], propargyl [102, 103, 104], amines [105, 106], cyano or nitrile, azido [65,107], trialkoxysilanes [108,109], or carbonates [110] to name a few. Though this present review is not devoted to detailing all functionalities, the more common ones are discussed in this section. The unique syntheses mentioned above are listed in **Scheme 10**. Typically iodides are made by reacting the acyl fluoride with lithium iodide and then heating to 180 °C to decarbonylate the polymer. The reaction is radically terminated by

the iodine radical which is produced during the heating of the intermediate acyl iodide. Alkylcarboxylates are obtained directly from the acyl fluoride by adding an alcohol of a given carbon length. Following, the alkyl carboxylates are reduced with either NaBH₄ or lithium aluminum hydride (LAH) to produce the methylene alcohols (hydroxyl). The nitrile groups are achieved by the dehydration of an amide using perfluoracetic anhydride as dehydration agent. Typically, the prior amide is established by reacting the ester with anhydrous ammonia gas to kick off an alcohol. As for PFPAEs bearing propargyl end-groups, they are obtained by a simple etherification of hydroxytelechelic oligo(HFPO) with propargyl bromide reported by Guan *et al.* [102] and then Lopez *et al.* [104] . The bis(trialkoxysilane) derivatives can be prepared by a condensation reaction of telechelic PFPEs methyl esters with an amino-trialkoxysilane alkane [108,109](**Scheme 10**).

Abbreviations : IPA =isopropyl alcohol, THF = tetrahydrofuran, HFB =hexafluorobenzene, HFX =hexafluoroxylene, E1 = CF₃CF₂CF₂OCHFClF₃, DMF =dimethylformamide

Scheme 10: Examples of telechelic PFPAE derivatives (Note: products from reactions 2 and 3 are commercially available).

Additional functional groups based upon alcohols, epoxides, olefins, and alkyl halides can be produced (**Table 9**) using a phase transfer catalysis process using either catalytic or stoichiometric amounts of *t*-butyl alcohol and its corresponding conjugate base (potassium *t*-butoxide)[17,47,50].

Table 9 : Phase transfer catalysis (PTC) transformation of telechelic PFPAE alcohols (adapted from J Fluorine Chem. 1999;95: 97-103) [17].

Electrophilic agent	Syntheses condition	Product	Ref.
	<i>t</i> -BuOK/ <i>t</i> -BuOH(catalytic)	$\text{Rf} \left[\text{CF}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O})_n\text{H} \right]_2$	17
	<i>t</i> -BuOK/ <i>t</i> -BuOH(catalytic)	$\text{Rf} \left[\text{CF}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OCH}_2\overset{\text{OH}}{\text{C}}\text{HOCH}_2\text{OH} \right]_2$	17
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>t</i>-BuOK/<i>t</i>-BuOH(catalytic) PTC Process 	$\text{Rf} \left[\text{CF}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O} \text{---} \text{CH}_2\text{---} \text{epoxide} \right]_2$	50
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>t</i>-BuOK/<i>t</i>-BuOH(catalytic) PTC Process 	$\text{Rf} \left[\text{CF}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O} \text{---} \text{CH}_2\text{---} \text{CH}=\text{CH}_2 \right]_2$	50
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>t</i>-BuOK/<i>t</i>-BuOH(catalytic) PTC Process 	$\text{Rf} \left[\text{CF}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O} \text{---} \text{CH}_2\text{---} \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{---} \text{CH}=\text{CH}_2 \right]_2$	111
$\text{Br}(\text{CH}_2)_m\text{Br}$	<i>t</i> -BuOK/ <i>t</i> -BuOH(catalytic)	$\text{Rf} \left[\text{CF}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_m\text{Br} \right]_2$	17

6. Materials based on Telechelic PFPAEs

Prior to supplying applications (Section 7), many materials that contain PFPAE segments have been reported according to various synthetic strategies.

6.1 Formation of Fluoroelastomers

Condensation reactions are very useful techniques to produce well-defined copolymers. In this sub-section, polycondensation pathways will be discussed as well as materials that can be photopolymerized.

6.1.1 Polycondensation reactions (polyurethanes, polyesters, polyethers, polyamides, and polycarbonates) to form multiblock copolymers

Various teams [112,113,114,115] have described the synthesis of pre-polymers and polymers to lead to polyurethanes, polyesters, polyethers, polyamides, and polypolycarbonates (**Scheme 1**) based on condensation reactions using telechelic diol

PFPAs. Several strategies were investigated to prepare fluorinated multiblock copolymers from these hydroxytelechelic PFPEs. The first generation was suggested by Tonelli *et al.* [49] for original fluorinated polyurethanes containing a Fomblin®-based PFPAE sequence as depicted in **Scheme 11**. Also, Turri's team summarized in an interesting book chapter [116], a comprehensive review on polyurethanes and polyureas based on telechelic diol and diamine PFPAs and they studied their thermal and surface properties.

Scheme 11: Synthesis of Polyurethane multiblock prepolymers based on PFPAs (adapted from J Appl Polym Sci. 1996;59(2):311–327) [49].

Li *et al.* [117] developed an original fluorinated self-healing polymer by the decoration of 2-ureido-4[1H]-pyrimidinone end groups on low average molecular weight PFPAs. The supramolecular polymers are networked by hydrogen bonding, providing enhanced modulus of elasticity and demonstrating a rapid self-healing. The authors suggested that their applications can be utilized in immersing fields of lubrication. To accomplish the reported target materials, they first added 2-amino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine onto 1,6-diisocyanatohexane and heated at 100 °C. Next, poly(tetrafluoroethylene oxide-co-difluoroethylene oxide) α,ω -diol, ethoxylated ($M_n \sim 2200 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) was added to 2-(6-isocyanatohexylaminocarbonylamino)-6-methyl-4[1H]pyrimidinone **1** with a catalytic amount of dibutyltin dilaurate (DBTDL) and heated to form the desired product, PFPE-UPy **2**. To form PFPE-UPy-Bn **3**, benzyl chloride and potassium carbonate were added in DMF with compound **2** and also heated (**Scheme 12**).

Scheme 12 : Formation of PFPAE self-healing polymers (reproduced by permission from J Poly Science, Part A : Poly Chem. 2013 ;51 :3598–3606) [117].

Pilati *et al.* [118] accomplished multiblock copolymers of PFPAEs containing polyester segments. The polycondensation of telechelic PFPAE diols, dimethylesters, or dicarboxylates with equimolar mixture of dimethyl terephthalate (DMT) and dimethyl isophthalate (DMI), with ethylene glycol (EG) ; or dimethyl terephthalate alone was achieved using $\text{Ti}(\text{O}i\text{Bu})_4$ as a catalyst. They found that the best yields of polyester was made using Fomblin® Z DOL TX (Scheme 13).

Scheme 13 : Formation of a PFPAE ester using dimethylterphthalate with Fomblin® Z DOL TX and $\text{Ti}(\text{O}i\text{Bu})_4$ as a catalyst (adapted from Polymer Bulletin.1992;28(2):151–157) [118].

The work by Levi and Turri [119] regarding polycarbonates focuses on two objectives: i) to understand the unusual polycondensation process in the frame of a classical macromolecular chemistry approach and ii) to achieve sustainable high molecular weight perfluorinated chain extended PFPAE polymers. The synthesis of PFPAE-polycarbonates is a

melt transesterification reaction occurring between diphenyl carbonate and poly-perfluoro(oxymethylene-*ran*-oxyethylene)dimethylol terminated oligomers providing linear, highly fluorinated polycarbonates (**Scheme 14**). The polycondensation is catalysed by $Zn(Ac)_2$ at higher temperatures. The polymerizations could be carried out in a closed systems with no by-product distillation. When the reaction is in non-equilibrium conditions, high purity macromonomers could be formed [119].

Scheme 14 : Polycondensation reaction between telechelic diol PFPAEs and diphenylcarbonate (reproduced with permission from *J Fluorine Chem.* 2004;125:339–344) [119].

PFPAE esters can easily react with primary and secondary amines without additional ester activation, due to the increased nucleophilicity of the carbonyl by the electron withdrawing effect of neighboring fluorine atoms. In the work of Patrick *et al.* [120] the Boc-protected dye was purified by reversed phase HPLC, and then deprotected with trifluoroacetic acid. The dye was then conjugated to the highly reactive PFPAE ester to form the necessary amide linker (**Scheme 15**). The material can be used intracellular pH measurements in living cells via fluorescent microscopy. Similar reactions can be used to convert the material into a nanoemulsion for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) as well.

Scheme 15 : Synthesis of CBPAs. Each CBPA is a mixture of PFPAE derivatives where cyanine is Cy3, Cy5, or CypHer5 fluorogen and composition of each CBPA is: Cy3-PFPE-oil (12, 15, and 18), Cy5-PFPE-oil (13, 16, and 18) and CypHer5-PFPE-oil (14, 17, and 18) (Reproduced with permission from J Am Chem Soc. 2013;135 (49):18445–18457) [120].

6.1.2 Reactive Macromonomers for radical or photo-polymerization [telechelic bis(meth)acrylates and bisstyrenes]

The design of UV-curable telechelic oligomers having the general structure G–R_n–PFPAE–R_n–G (where G enables the UV polymerization) has been reported by several research teams: Tonelli *et al.* [121,122], Bongiovanni *et al.* [123,124,125] and DeSimone *et al.* [126,127,128]. Diol PFPAEs undergoing condensation reactions with isocyanates, anhydrides, or acryloyl chloride catalyzed by trimethylamine [103] are the most common methods to allow the preparation of UV-curable PFPAEs.

For example, DeSimone's group [126] synthesized and photopolymerized telechelic bis(methacrylate)s containing PFPAE units. The methacrylation of PFPAEs was accomplished by the condensation of 2-isocyanatoethyl methacrylate (IEM) with telechelic bis(hydroxy) PFPAEs, as precursors to photocrosslinked networks based on PFPAEs containing urethane bridges (Scheme 16).

Scheme 16 : Structures of fluorinated telechelic bis(meth)acrylates based on perfluoropolyethers, obtained by condensation of PFPPE diols and 2-isocyanatoethyl methacrylate (reproduced with permission from J Am Chem Soc. 2004;126:2322-2323) [126].

Though cross-linked, the resulting networks depicted in **Scheme 16** display very low T_g values (ca. -100 °C, assessed by DMA analysis), as evidenced from the insertion of soft PFPPEs central chains far removed from the crosslinking knots made by the methacrylates units embedded within the matrix.

Bongiovanni's team [129] introduced end groups G, from the general structure, as an acrylate or a methacrylate photoreactive group and R_h as a hydrogenated spacer. To extend the $\text{HOCH}_2\text{CF}_2\text{O(CF}_2\text{O)}_q\text{(CF}_2\text{CF}_2\text{O)}_p\text{CF}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ diol with a hydrocarbon block (R_h), various diisocyanates were used such as 2-isocyanatoethyl methacrylate (IEM), trimethylhexamethylenediisocyanate (TMDI) (containing an equimolar mixture of 2,2,4-TMDI and 2,4,4-TMDI isomers followed by 2-hydroxyethyl acrylate (HEA), as well as isophorone diisocyanate (IPDI). This same study also reported the synthesis of a highly fluorinated UV-curable oligomer from the direct reaction of hydroxyl telechelic PFPPE with an excess of methacrylic anhydride. However, the reactivity of that obtained dimethacrylic oligomer was quite low, arising probably from the poor solubility of the photoinitiators or from some color that absorbed the UV irradiation. R_h was introduced to tailor the properties of the binder and of the final coating after curing. Because of the more polar hydrogenated moieties, it helped to tune the main properties of the oligomers, such as viscosity, refractive index,

mechanical properties and compatibility with other monomers and chemicals [129](Scheme 17).

Scheme 17 : Telechelic bis(meth)acrylate or bis(methacrylamido) PFPAE by modification of FLK D10H: 5097X from (methacrylic anhydride), 5088X from (2-isocyanatoethyl methacrylate, IEM), 5090X from (isophorone diisocyanate,IPDI), 5105X from(trimethylhexamethylene diisocyanate (TMDI) followed by 2-hydroxyethyl acrylate (HEA)) (adapted from from Polym Int. 2012;61(1):65-73) [129].

Bongiovanni's group [123] revisited that route and they noted that the PFPAE urethane bis(methacrylate)s displayed two amorphous thermal phases assigned to fluorinated and hydrogenated counterparts. These original telechelic macromonomers were photopolymerized and the authors monitored the process by IR and NMR spectroscopy. Vitale *et al.* [130] also reviewed photocrosslinking in term of the natures of the photoinitiator, the telechelic fluorinated resins, reactive diluents, viscosity adjustment, and other experimental conditions.

An example of reactive diluent to react with PFPAE methacrylates was illustrated by Hu *et al.* [131] using a dimethacrylate based on poly(ethylene oxide), PEO, to achieve amphiphilic networks (**Scheme 18**).

Scheme 18 : Synthetic Scheme of PFPE/PEO Networks via a Precursor Approach. (reproduced with permission from J Am Chem Soc. 2008;130 :14244–14252) [131].

The newly formed amphiphilic PFPE/PEO networks has a dual advantage to be a potential non-fouling coating material due to the high durability of PFPAE and the non-fouling properties of PEO, but also an optically transparent film (**Figure 13**).

Fig. 13. Optically transparent and opaque films of PFPAE-PEO (PEG) methacrylates. Text placed underneath the polymer is legible only for the transparent films [131]. Copyright 2008, Reproduced with permission from ACS Publications.

Another interesting example of difunctional fluorinated PFPAE oligomers was reported by Bongiovanni's group [132] where the reactive functions are both acrylic and allylic. The allylic groups served two purposes: (1) reacting with oxygen in the presence of radicals to produce hydroperoxides thus preventing oxygen inhibition and (2) improving the

surface cure, while the acrylic group mainly ensured the bulk cure. First, the PFPAE diol was reacted with an excess of IPDI in the presence of a tin catalyst to lead to isocyanato-terminated prepolymer (monitored by ^{19}F -NMR spectroscopy). Subsequently, the fluorinated prepolymer was end functionalized with different hydroxy-unsaturated reactants, used in different ratios, i.e hydroxypropyl acrylate and trimethylolpropane diallylether (**Scheme 19**). The synthesized product was a mixture composed of a diacrylate (Resin A) that has a reactive group content (RGC) of $1.19 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, a polyallylic product (Resin B) with a $\text{RGC}=2.16 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, and a multifunctional product with both acrylic and allylic functionalities (Resin C) of $\text{RGC}=0.686 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ and $0.914 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, respectively [132].

Scheme 19 : Telechelic bis(acrylate) [Resin A], bis(allyl) [Resin B] and mixed allyl/acrylate [Resin C] utilizing PFPAEs (adapted from *Pigm. Resin Technol.* 1999, 28, 212-216) [132].

More recently, De Marco *et al.* [133] designed a new PFPAE-based resin (**Scheme 20**), synthesized and employed for the successful fabrication of submicrometer 3D structures by two photon polymerization (2PP) technology. The first part of the reaction took place with the PFPAE-diol added dropwise to an excess of isophorone diisocyanate (IPDI), and DBTDL as the catalyst. After being formed, the telechelic IPDI was finally reacted with pentaerythritol triacrylate to form the desired macromomer. The photoinitiator, Lucirin TPO-L, was used to produce the desired cross-linked material.

Scheme 20 : Structures of PFPAGE resin having six acrylate functions to be photocured for 3D microfluidic networks (adapted from Langmuir. 2013;29:426–431) [133].

The PFPAGE resist, being intrinsically hydrophobic and chemically resistant, can be used to manufacture 3D functional microfluidic devices requiring a good chemical resistance, and to fabricate hydrophobic tips for AFM, optimizing the imaging of wet and biological samples. This quite interesting study is regarded as the first example of 3D microfabrication of hydrophobic and chemical resistant submicrometric structures (see section 7, **Figure 56**).

Lopez *et. al.* [134] prepared networks composed of PFPAGE and poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF), in which the PFPE was crosslinked with PVDF through the copolymerization of polymethacrylates. A telechelic PFPE-dimethacrylate (PFPE-DMA) and the 4-arm star PVDF methacrylate prepared by RAFT polymerization of VDF with a tetraxanthate (**Scheme 21**) were mixed at different weight ratios and then photocrosslinked. By adding the PFPAGE, the water contact angles increased from the expected value of 80° for PVDF to 120° for that achieved from initial PFPAGE : PVDF 5 : 1 (w : w). The surface energy of the coating was calculated to be 8 mN·m⁻¹.

Scheme 21: Photoinduced copolymerization of fluorinated poly(methacrylates) used to form PFPAAE-PVDF star-based polymers (reproduced with permission from Polym Chem. 2017;8 :3045-3049) [134].

DeSimone *et al.* [111], using methods reported earlier on intermediate telechelic PFPAAE, were able to demonstrate that photochemical copolymerization of telechelic bis(styrene) PFPAAE with a 4-fluorinated sulfonate styrene, followed by hydrolysis, could lead to a cross-linked membrane for fuel cells with a high degree of surface area. The sulphonic acid function enables high ionic exchange capacities, and the network being also fluorinated enhances its superhydrophobicity (**Scheme 22**).

Scheme 22 : Cross-linking of telechelic bis(styrene) PFPAE with a 4-fluorinated sulfonate styrene (reproduced with permission from J Am Chem Soc. 2006;128 (39):12963–12972) [111].

6.2 Triblock or Multiblock Copolymer Materials

Hydroxytelechelic PFPAEs are quite valuable precursors to design many well-defined fluoropolymers, such as triblock and multiblock copolymers, crosslinked networks, interpenetrated polymer networks (IPNs), as illustrated in this section.

6.2.1 PEO-*b*-PFPAE-*b*-PEO Triblock Copolymers

Several examples of triblock copolymers based on PFPAEs have been reported. The ring opening polymerization of ethylene oxide (EO) leads to PEO-*b*-PFPE-*b*-PEO triblock copolymers containing PEO, the average molecular weights of which are ca. 2000 g·mol⁻¹. These products are nowadays marketed by Solvay Specialty Polymers under the Fluorolink® tradename [135]. Regarding academic examples, triblock copolymers based on PFPE (B) and PEO (A) were made. PEO-*b*-PFPE-*b*-PEO (P1–P3) and PFPE-*b*-PEG-*b*-PFPE (P4–P5) were prepared via thiol–ene click reaction (**Scheme 23**) in high yields [136]. The A–B–A conformation triblock copolymers (P1–P3) were synthesized using telechelic PFPAE diols in a Williamson synthesis from the diol onto allyl bromide. The telechelic PFPAE bis(allylethers) and the PEO (mono)thiol were connected through a thiol–ene click reaction to form the desired PEO-*b*-PFPAE-*b*-PEO triblock copolymers. This can be accomplished through radical addition initiated by azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN).

Scheme 23 : Thiol–ene click reaction using di- or mono-PFPAE allylethers and di- or mono-functional PEO thiols (reproduced with permission from RSC Adv. 2015;5:64170-64179) [136].

In another strategy, reported by Lopez *et al.* [65], the synthesis of an amphiphilic PEO-*b*-PFPAE-*b*-PEO triblock copolymer containing PEO2000 end-blocks and a PFPAE1200 central sequence was obtained using a copper(I)-catalyzed alkyne–azide cycloaddition between a telechelic PFPAE bis(alkyne) and ω -azido PEO (**Scheme 24**).

Scheme 24 : Top) Copper(I)-catalyzed “click” chemistry between PFPAE–diyne **1** and PEO–azide **2** in order to create amphiphilic PEO-*b*-PFPE-*b*-PEO triblock copolymer. Bottom) Self-assembly of triblock in water to form a micelle (reproduced with permission from RSC Polym Chem. 2016;7:402-409) [65].

Such an A-B-A triblock copolymer was characterized by ¹H-, ¹⁹F-NMR and diffusion-ordered spectroscopy (DOSY). The ¹H DOSY NMR experiment (**Figure 14**) gave evidenced for the absence of any remaining homopolymers by the determination of the different DOSY diffusion coefficients (D): 6.31 × 10⁻¹⁰, 2.138 × 10⁻¹⁰, and 1.862 × 10⁻¹⁰ for telechelic PFPAE, PEO-azide and PEO-*b*-PFPAE-*b*-PEO triblock copolymer, respectively.

Figure 14 : ^1H DOSY-NMR spectra (recorded in CD_3OD) of PEG2000-*b*-PFPAE1200-*b*-PEG2000 (top spectrum), telechelic PEG-azide 2 (blue insert left), PFPAE-diyne 1 (red insert right). (reproduced with permission from RSC Polym Chem. 2016;7:402-409) [65].

The resulting PEO₂₀₀₀-*b*-PFPE₁₂₀₀-*b*-PEO₂₀₀₀ triblock copolymer displayed a satisfactory thermal stability under air with no weight loss up to 275 °C, also enhanced by robust triazole rings. In addition, such a triblock copolymer underwent self-assembly into micelles ($D = 10\text{--}20$ nm) in aqueous solution, as confirmed from cryogenic-temperature transmission electron microscopy (**Figure 15**). The CMC was determined to be $0.1\text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ [65].

Fig. 15. Cryo-TEM image of the aqueous PEO₂₀₀₀-*b*-PFPAE₁₂₀₀-*b*-PEO₂₀₀₀ triblock copolymer (50 mg mL⁻¹) [65]. Copyright 2016, Reproduced with permission from Royal Society of Chemistry.

Kressler *et al.* [137] used slightly different synthetic methodology to produce triblock copolymers PEO-*b*-PHFPO-*b*-PEO. First, these authors synthesized the telechelic diacylfluoride PFPAE using hexafluoroglutaridyl fluoride and polymerized HFPO from it. Through a series of steps (**Scheme 25**), the PFPAEs were converted to yield the targeted fluorinated enamine. Then, a monofunctional PEO could be easily attached to form the triblock copolymers. TEM images showed supramolecular aggregates of PEO-*b*-PHFPO-*b*-PEO triblock copolymers on carbon coated copper after transferring it to water solutions. Spherical micelles as well as cylindrical elongated aggregates in the nm-range could be observed.

Scheme 25 : Synthesis of PEO-*b*-PHFPO-*b*-PEO triblock copolymer (reproduced with permission from Polymer Preprints. 2005;46(2):580) [137].

6.2.2 Synthesis of PFPAE-*b*-PEO-*b*-PFPAE triblock Copolymers

Although not telechelic, but important for comparison purposes, hydrophobic-*b*-hydrophilic-*b*-hydrophobic triblock copolymers, such as PFPAE-*b*-PEO-*b*-PFPAE (FOF) [138] and PB (1,2-polybutadiene)-*b*-PEO-*b*-PFPAE (BOF) were synthesized. Their average molecular weights were 2.3-23-2.3 (in kg·mol⁻¹) and 1.9-26-2.3, respectively (Scheme 26). A polymer-polymer coupling reaction between a telechelic bis(hydroxyl) PEO and a PFPAE bearing a single acid chloride end-group was used to form FOF. Commercially available carboxylic PFPAE was converted into the acyl chloride derivative using oxalyl chloride. BOF was produced from taking PB-*b*-PEO diblock copolymers, obtained by two successive living anionic polymerizations, and terminating the polymer with acidic methanol, yielding a hydroxyl-terminated diblock copolymer. The final BOF terpolymer was obtained by coupling the hydroxy end-functional PB-PEO with the acid chloride end-functional PFPAE.

Scheme 26 : Triblock copolymers of PFPAE-*b*-PEO-*b*-PFPAE (FOF) and PB-*b*-PEO-*b*-PFPAE (BOF) (reproduced with permission from *Macromolecules*. 2010;43 :5396–5404) [138].

Lodge's group [138] studied the dependence of morphology of these triblock polymer hydrogels on the chemical identity of the end-blocks. These triblock copolymers formed networks by aggregation of the end-blocks and such resulting gels with polymer concentrations ranging from 10 to 30 wt% were characterized by means of cryogenic cryo-SEM and small-angle neutron scattering (SANS). Cryo-SEM images (**Figure 16**) revealed significant differences among the morphologies of the hydrogels. The triblock 10% solution displays a network of disk-like micelles, also with large voids, whereas the 30% solution resembles an open cell foam. Results from contrast matching SANS experiments were used to corroborate and refine the information obtained from microscopy. This was attributed to the high interfacial tension of PFPAE with water and is consistent with the "super-strong" segregation regime behavior. With similar blocks at both ends, the curvature of the

hydrophobic domains and hence the network morphology was driven by the high interfacial tension between the hydrophobic blocks and water, compared with their hydrocarbon counterparts. The PB-*b*-PEO-*b*-PFPAE triblock copolymer adopted a much different structure. It produced continuous open-cell foam with cells in the order of 500 nm in size and PFPAE disks embedded in PB sheets. Both polymers demonstrate that end-block chemistry can be used to manipulate equally the morphology and physical properties of the polymer gels.

Fig. 16. Cryo-SEM micrographs of aqueous solutions of (c) 10 wt% FOF, (d) 30 wt% FOF, (e) 10 wt% BOF, and (f) 30 wt% BOF [138]. Copyright 2010, Reproduced with permission from ACS Publications.

6.2.3 Synthesis of Poly(M)-*b*-PFPAE-*b*-Poly(M) Triblock Copolymers from Telechelic PFPAEs

Pilati *et al.* [139] pioneered the synthesis of PCL-*b*-PFPAE-*b*-PCL triblock copolymers by the ROP of ϵ -caprolactone (CL) from telechelic bis(hydroxyl) PFPAEs (Fomblin[®]ZDOL TX) ranging from 1100, 2200, to 3400 g·mol⁻¹. The ROP produced such triblock copolymers containing short PCL sequences ranging from 4 to 7 units. Such a strategy was also inspired by Smith's group [140,141] who reported the preparation of PLA-*b*-PFPE-*b*-PLA triblock copolymers of various average molecular weights (1.5-4.2 kg·mol⁻¹) from the ROP of L-lactide

(LA) initiated by telechelic bis(hydroxyl) PFPAs in the presence of tin(II) 2-ethylhexanoate, as displayed in **Scheme 27**:

Scheme 27 : Synthesis of PLA-*b*-PFPAE-*b*-PLA triblock copolymers using bis(hydroxyl) PFPAs to ring open polymerize L-lactide (reproduced with permission from Polym. Int. 2011;60:507–516) [140].

These authors assessed the fluid contact angles (FCAs). The water (polar solvent) and methylene iodide and n-hexadecane (apolar solvents) contact angles ranged between 104.2 and 104.7, 73.7 to 75.8, and 58.8 to 60.6, respectively. In addition to the work of contact angles, adhesion tests were conducted and showed that adhesion decreased for the triblock copolymers compared to those of the PLA (**Figure 17**).

Fig. 17. PLA-*b*-PFPE-*b*-PLA triblock copolymers of various average molecular weights and their adhesion results in various solvents [140]. Copyright 2011, Reproduced with permission from John Wiley & Sons Ltd.

6.3. Synthesis of Crosslinked Materials Based on PFPAEs

Cross-linked PFPAEs can be useful in producing alkaline electrolytes for zinc-air batteries, to anti-fouling coatings and to high temperature elastomers. Photopolymerization of (meth)acrylates and “click” chemistry are typical synthetic pathways to generate these desired materials.

6.3.1 Photocrosslinked Telechelic Bis(meth)acrylates for Interpenetrated Polymer Networks (IPNs)

Original interpenetrated polymer networks (IPN) architecture combining a hydrogenated cationic polyelectrolyte based on poly(epichlorohydrin) (PECH) and a PFPAE for the development of alkaline electrolytes for zinc-air batteries as storage or production energy systems were reported by Bertolotti *et al.* [142]. This team studied novel anion exchange membranes (used in efficient membrane/air electrode assembly) to protect air electrodes operating in aqueous lithium-air battery configuration, i.e. supplied with atmospheric air and in concentrated aqueous lithium hydroxide (**Figure 18**). These protective IPN membranes were composed of two co-continuous phases, each one rich in one of the polymer in the materials. Such a morphology enabled the authors to combine their properties from the weight proportions of each polymer.

Thus, PECH/PFPE IPNs displayed interesting features: water uptake varying from 30 to 90 wt%, ionic (OH⁻) conductivity ranging from 1 to 2 mS·cm⁻¹, and an anionic transport number from 0.65 to 0.80 when the PECH proportion varied from 40 to 90 wt%. These membranes were assembled onto electrodes. These ladders protected with a 70/30 PECH/PFPE IPN exhibited outstanding stability (> 1000 h, i.e. a 20-fold lifetime increase of the non-modified electrodes).

Fig. 18. Sketch of the synthesis of poly(epichlorohydrin) (PECH)/PFPAE interpenetrated polymer networks [142]. Copyright 2015, Reproduced with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd.

DeSimone's team [143] using tetraols of PFPAEs, designed successful tetramethacryloxy-modified PFPAEs (PFPAE-TMA) that could be photochemically cross-linked in one step using UV irradiation. The new fluorinated network displayed an improved modulus (155–458 MPa) compared to networks made with polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) or other fluorinated elastomer materials. Partial miscibility of PFPAE-TMA macromonomer with 1H, 1H, 6H, 6H-perfluoro-1,6-hexyldiacrylate (PFHDA) was evident due to the hydrogen bonding and dispersive interactions between the urethane ether methacrylate and fluorinated acrylate groups. The mixture ratio was found to be essential to develop clear solutions or immiscible systems. If PFHDA of <40 wt% was mixed with the PFPAE-TMA macromonomer, the solution was clear and homogeneous. If PFHDA was greater than 40 wt%, the system was immiscible. Improvements in miscibility with high PFDA loading could be achieved only at elevated temperatures. Optically transparent samples were easily obtained with 40 wt% PFHDA at room temperature and with PFHDA content larger than 40 wt% by controlling the cure temperature above the corresponding cloud-point temperature of the system. The UV polymerized materials had low surface tensions (14.3–17.5 mN·m⁻¹) and were reported as materials suitable for enhanced fouling-release coating applications [143](Scheme 28).

Scheme 28 : Synthesis of IPN based on PFPAE tetramethacrylate macromonomer and a telechelic fluorinated PFHDA (reproduced with permission from *Macromolecules*. 2010;43:10397–10405) [143].

From the similar strategy, the same team [6] was able to photochemically cross-link by UV-curing high-performance PFPAE elastomers containing either methacrylate or styrene end-groups in one step using a series of reactive liquid PFPAE precursors. The PFPAE molecular structure was investigated in how it correlated to bulk and surface properties, thermal stability, contact angle/surface tension, modulus, and biofouling behavior (**Scheme 29**).

Scheme 29 : Chemical Structures of PFPAE Macromonomers: (a) telechelic bis(methacrylate) PFPAE, (b) telechelic bis(methacrylate) 2 X PFPE, (c) telechelic bis(methacrylate) 3 × PFPAE, (d) telechelic bis(styrene) PFPAE, and (e) Fluorinated styrene sulfonic ester (reproduced with permission from *Macromolecules*. 2009;42(18):6999–7007)[6].

6.3.2 Alkyne-Azide “click” Chemistry with Trifunctional Derivatives

Using alkyne-azide Huisgen cycloaddition or “click” chemistry, can afford novel but robust elastomers. The “click” chemistry can be accomplished with high efficiency therefore producing a viable polymer for fabrication [144]. Yang *et al.* [102] found that the 1,2,3-triazole linkages were very stable to harsh acidic or basic conditions. Actually, with the insertion of telechelic PFPAE propargyl onto an aromatic triazido derivative using “click” polymerization (**Scheme 30**), the newly created material comprising the 2,2,3-triazole function contained a unique design feature in the polymer that makes the material remarkably resistant to heat and to a large variety of organic solvents. The elastomeric material showed strong adhesion to glass and overcame numbers of disadvantages other materials have encountered when fabricating microfluidic devices, such as PDMS and earlier reported PFPAE gels. The research group envisioned that the “clicked” PFPAE elastomers would be excellent candidates for microfluidic applications [145].

Scheme 30 : Synthesis of crosslinked PFPAs in the presence of triazido crosslinking agent via a copper catalyzed alkyne-azide click chemistry (reproduced with permission from *J Chem Mat.* 2012; 22:1100) [102].

Typically, polymers containing repeating units derived from chosen fluorinated olefins are used for making fluoroelastomers [3,10], which subsequently are cured to gain elastomeric properties. Unfortunately, these types of fluoroelastomers are solids and are cumbersome to process. Some new methodology has arisen also using the alkyne-azide “click” chemistry in 2014. First, 3M utilized a method involving telechelic methyl esters of PFPAs and reacted it with propargyl amine to yield telechelic bis(propargyl) amido PFPAs (**A**). The cross-linker (**B**) was formed from epichlorohydrin and trimethylol propane (**Scheme 31**) [103].

Scheme 31 : 3M Company's strategy for low temperature elastomers using PFPAs (**A**) in the presence of triazido derivative (**B**) obtained from epichlorohydrin and trimethylolpropane (adapted from 2014 WO 2014055406 A2) [103].

Since epichlorohydrin is considered toxic, Charlas *et. al.* [146] overcame this issue by using a triazido derivative from tris(bromomethyl)propanol. Fomblin[®]-ZDOL reacted with tosyl chloride, in order to be a good leaving group for the sodium azide nucleophile (**Scheme**

32). Fomblin®-ZDOL also underwent an etherification with propargyl bromide in basic conditions to form the telechelic bis(propargyl) PFPAE.

Scheme 32 : Steps required to form telechelic PFPAE azides (reproduced with permission from 2017 WO 2017001806 A1) [146].

With the combination of these telechelic PFPAEs, the materials were “clicked” together to form a wide range of materials from elastomers to very viscous polymers. In a later patent, Charlas *et al.* [146] used a pentaerythritol triazide as a crosslinking agents with telechelic bis(propargyl) PFPAE to form elastomeric materials endowed with low T_g s and high temperature performance (**Scheme 33**).

Scheme 33 : alkyne-azide “click” chemistry of telechelic PFPAE bispropargyl with pentaerythritol triazide (reproduced with permission from 2017 WO 2017001806 A1) [146].

6.3.3 Polyhydrosilylation of Telechelic PFPAE dienes with Telechelic Bis(silane)s

The alkenyl-containing PFPAE serves as a building block in many compositions, including ion-conducting polymer electrolyte membranes [63], and largely affects the strength of the material. Such PFPAE formulations are claimed in various patents [147,148,149] to allow for PFPAE-b-PDMS multiblock copolymers (**Scheme 34**). They are

commercially available under the SIFEL[®] trade name marketed by Shin-Etsu Chemical Co., Ltd. These fluorinated silicones are classified in terms of their ability to form liquid rubber compositions and millable rubber structures. For integral molding, the rubbers feature an ease of handling and simple mold configurations, which are more desirable than the liquid injected molding silanes (LIMS) compositions that require complex mold configurations.

Scheme 34 : One example of the synthetic procedures to form a product in the SIFEL[®] series.

Combining PFPAE and dimethylsiloxane moieties (**Scheme 34**) enables Sifel[®] product to withstand exceptional properties at low temperature.

7. Applications of Telechelic PFPAEs

PFPAES have been incorporation into many innovative materials for various specific applications. These include areas such as hydrogels, antibacterial and self-assembly coatings, multidrug resistance reversal systems, as well as high-tech devices for aerospace as high performance thermoplastic elastomers, photoresists, microfluidics or products for lithography. They are endowed with exceptional surface properties which also include antifouling and de-icing coatings, and new components for energy such as fuel cells or electrolytes for zinc-air and lithium ion batteries that are discussed hereafter.

7.1 Self-Assembly Materials

Evaluating PEO₂₀₀₀-*b*-PFPE₁₂₀₀-*b*-PEO₂₀₀₀ triblock copolymers designed through the “click” method (**Scheme 24**), revealed a decomposition temperature of 325 °C at 10% weight loss, under air (**Figure 19**) and a melting temperature (T_m) of 40 °C. When analyzed by cryo-TEM (**Figure 15**), a corresponding image that clearly evidenced the formation of nearly monodisperse spherical micelles of diameters in the range of 10–15 nm.

Fig. 19. TGA thermogram overlay of the $\text{PEO}_{2000}\text{-}b\text{-PFPE}_{1200}\text{-}b\text{-PEO}_{2000}$ triblock copolymer (black curve) compared to those of PEO-azide 2 (blue curve), and PFPAE-diyne 1 (red curve), under air. The strategy of synthesis of the triblock is displayed in Scheme 24 [65]. Copyright 2016, Reproduced with permission from Royal Society of Chemistry.

The CMC of such $\text{PEO}_{2000}\text{-}b\text{-PFPE}_{1200}\text{-}b\text{-PEO}_{2000}$ triblock copolymer in water, was determined by fluorimetry conducted in emission mode with an excitation wavelength tuned to 340 nm. Pyrene was used as the fluorescent probe. The intensity ratio (I_3/I_1) in pyrene emission spectra (Figure 20) enabled to assess the CMC to be $0.1 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ [65]. In further development of this work, the research group aims at evaluating these triblock copolymers as an electrolyte for Li-ion batteries.

Fig. 20. Fluorescent versus the copolymer concentration to determine the critical micelle concentration [65]. Copyright 2016, Reproduced with permission from Royal Society of Chemistry.

As for PLA-*b*-PFPE-*b*-PLA triblock copolymers (FluoroPLAs), the glass transition, melting, crystallization and degradation temperatures for such FluoroPLAs completely depend on the PFPAE segment length (**Table 10**). All the transition temperatures follow the trend: $T_{\text{PLA}} > T_{\text{FluoroPLA}(4.2\text{k})} > T_{\text{FluoroPLA}(2.0\text{k})} > T_{\text{FluoroPLA}(1.5\text{k})}$. As the PFPAE content increases from 0 to 4.6×10^{-3} mol, M_n decreases from 144 kg.mol⁻¹ (for PLA) to 68 kg.mol⁻¹ (for FluoroPLA (1.5k)) with dispersity (\bar{D}) in the 1.6–1.8 range [140].

When looking at the trends for heats of fusion and degrees of crystallization, the smaller PFPAE segments caused a large internal plasticization effect. The increase in crystallization of FluoroPLAs was possibly due to the nucleating behavior of PFPAE segments, which decreases the activation energy of diffusion of PLA segments at crystallization sites. Smaller PFPE segment domains, in glassy or crystalline form, at lower temperatures likely act as reinforcing domains for the PLA matrix [140].

Table 10 : Thermal analysis results for PLA and FluoroPLAs (adapted from Polym Int. 2011;60 :507–516) [140].

Polymer	Temperature (°C)				Enthalpy (J.g ⁻¹)	
	T_g^a	T_c^a	T_m^a	T_d^b	ΔH_f^a	ΔH_c^a
PLA	61	109	176	299	43	29
FluoroPLA(4.2K)	60	106	173	288	48	31
FluoroPLA(2.0K)	56	103	170	267	48	32
FluoroPLA(1.5K)	51	99	167	250	46	30

^aDSC data for quenched (however, the rate of crystallization is not zero) samples heated at a rate of 10 °C.min⁻¹, second heating cycle ^bTGA data for annealed films for 10% weight loss at a heating rate of 10 °C.min⁻¹

Surface energies dropped from 35–40 to 16–20 mN.m⁻¹ with little amounts of PFPAE. FluoroPLAs exhibited significant hydrophobic and lipophobic properties compared to PLA (**Table 11**). However, there was no considerable change in surface properties when comparing the various PFPAE chain lengths. As above, this arose from the overall fluorine content remaining nearly the same irrespective of block length. However, the surface energies of FluoroPLAs were comparable to that of PTFE. Therefore, FluoroPLAs have better hydrophobicity and lipophobicity than poly(lactides) [140]. These new polymers may find applications in novel low temperature resistant amphiphobic renewable material-based coatings and plastics.

Table 11 : Static contact angle values in degrees (mean^a ± standard deviation) for PLA and FluoroPLAs (adapted from Polym Int. 2011;60 :507–516) [140].

Polymer	Water	Glycerol	Formamide	Methylene Iodide	n-Hexadecane
PLA	74.3±0.6	70.6±1.9	59.4±0.7	39.9±0.3	22.6±2.0
FluoroPLA(4.2K)	104.2±0.5	96.2±2.5	89.6±1.7	73.7±0.3	58.8±1.9
FluoroPLA(2.0K)	104.1±0.4	99.2±1.0	94.1±0.5	77.5±1.0	58.8±2.7
FluoroPLA(1.5K)	104.7±0.5	101.2±0.4	93.3±1.1	75.8±0.8	60.6±4.1

a Mean of at least five measurements.

In other applications, PFPAEs have the ability to dramatically change the viscosity of a solution thus modifying its physical property. Triblock polymers containing PFPAE can be helpful in their ability to create a range of materials from viscous liquids to rubbery solids, such as hydrogels, which are completely dependent upon the chain architecture. For example, long hydrophilic central blocks such as PEO and short hydrophobic end-blocks such as PFPAE, at low copolymer concentrations, the PFPAE blocks associate to form micellar cores with block-looping or back-looping of the PEO, thus increasing the viscosity of the solution [138]. For higher concentrations of the triblock, increasing the number density of the micelles, the PEO central block could back-fold by bridging to another micellar core, steeply increasing viscosity to form a gel. Interestingly, the aqueous systems of PFPAE-*b*-PEO-*b*-PFPAE and PB-*b*-PEO-*b*-PFPAE display alternative ways of circumventing the enthalpic penalty of PFPAE/water interfaces. The PFPAE-*b*-PEO-*b*-PFPAE aqueous system did so by crowding the surface of disk with PEO chains, thereby expelling water from the interface, while the PB-*b*-PEO-*b*-PFPAE aqueous system associated the fluorinated shaped disks with the relatively less hydrophobic butadiene chains (**Figure 21**) [138]. Although not telechelic PFPAEs, these structures are helpful for a comparison framework. Also, these types of materials may find potential applications in the fields of coatings, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, and oil recovery.

Fig. 21. Schematic cartoon showing the dependence of network morphology on the end-groups. PEO, poly(butadiene), and PFPAE are represented in blue, red and green, respectively. The scale bars identify a length of 5 nm in each cartoon, PFPAE-*b*-PEO-*b*-PFPAE (left) and PB-*b*-PEO-*b*-PFPAE (right) [138]. Copyright 2010, Reproduced with permission from ACS Publications.

Another application of PFPAE triblock copolymers deals with the use of anti-bacterial materials. PEO is well-known for its ability to inhibit protein as well as cell adsorption. This is due to the electrostatic repulsion and a hydration effect at the interface. In **Table 12**, P1-P3 are PEO-*b*-PFPAE-*b*-PEO and P4-P5 are PFPAE-*b*-PEO-*b*-PFPAE triblock copolymers, respectively [136]. The table provides their compositions and the thermal decomposition (T_d) temperatures. The table shows that a smaller length of PFPAE ($M_w = 438-490 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) improves the thermal decomposition temperature for the specific conformation.

Table 12 : Compositions, average molecular weights, yields and thermal properties of P1–P5 (adapted from RSC Adv. 2015;5:64170-64179) [136].

Polymers	Conformation	PEG (A) M_w	PFPAE (B) M_w	Calc. M_w^a	Expt. M_n^b	PDI ^c	Yield (%)	Purity ^d (%)	T_d^e (°C)
P1	A-B-A	ca. 1000	490	2490	2250	1.16	95.0	95.0	284
P2		ca. 1000	ca. 2580	4580	4100	1.09	93.0	97.4	244
P3		ca. 2000	ca. 2580	6580	6181	1.12	90.0	94.5	270
P4	B-A-B	ca. 1000	438	1876	1774	1.08	97.0	97.6	254
P5		ca. 1000	ca. 3785	8570	7849	1.16	88.0	90.2	236

^a Calculated molecular weight. ^b Experimental number-average molecular weight from GPC. ^c Polydispersity index (PDI). ^d Polymer purity was estimated by ¹H NMR spectroscopy (ESI). ^e Thermal decomposition temperature (T_d) is defined as the temperature at which 5% weight loss occurs.

In Table 13, the relatively lower percentage of PFPAEs with PEO showed that P1-2 and P4 were more soluble in water and polar organic solvents such as ethanol, THF, chloroform, and acetone [136].

Table 13 : Solubility of polymers P1–P5 (adapted from RSC Adv. 2015;5:64170-64179) [136].

Solvent	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5
Water	☑	☑	–	☑	x
Ethanol	☑	☑	–	☑	x
Acetone	☑	☑	☑	☑	–
Chloroform	☑	☑	☑	☑	–
THF	☑	☑	–	☑	–
Hexane	x	x	–	x	–
FC-77®	x	x	–	x	☑

☑ soluble or dispersed well; –, poor; x, very poor

The morphology control originates from the balance between the isotropic coalescence and the anisotropic self-assembly of core–shell (micelle) particles. When a quick evaporation of solvent occurs, the block copolymer micelles concentrate and then aggregated. The shell layer of PEO block from different micelles collapse and coalesce to larger particles [136]. This process overcomes entropic penalties and increasing the overlap volume between the molecular chains on micelle shell layer. In attempt to overcome the penalty, the triblocks anisotropically assemble and form wrinkled-like structures for P1-P4 as displayed in **Figure 22** [136].

Fig. 22. SEM images of (a) P1; (b) P2; (c) P3; (d) P4; (e) P5 where P1-P3 and P4-P5 are PEO-*b*-PFPAE-*b*-PEO and PFPAE-*b*-PEO-*b*-PFPAE, respectively; and (f) neat PEO thin film morphology. Scale bar: 10 mm [136]. Copyright 2015, Reproduced with permission from Royal Society of Chemistry.

The self-assembly process is illustrated by a cartoon displayed in **Figure 23** and explains why P1-P3 copolymers have lower contact angles than those of P4-P5 (**Table 14**).

Figure 23 : Illustrative description on the self-assembly process of the triblock copolymers (P3 as example) [136]. Copyright 2015, Reproduced with permission from Royal Society of Chemistry.

Table 14 : Water contact angles for triblock copolymers (P1-P5) where P1-P3 and P4-P5 are PEO-*b*-PFPAE-*b*-PEO and PFPAE-*b*-PEO-*b*-PFPAE, respectively (adapted from RSC Adv. 2015;5:64170-64179) [136].

Polymer	Contact Angle (CA) (θ)
P1	12.3 \pm 1.7
P2	10.8 \pm 1.2
P3	10.6 \pm 1.5
P4	10.2 \pm 2.1
P5	58.5 \pm 4.3

The self-assembled micelle sizes of P1–P5 were in the range of 100–260 nm with broad particle size distributions. For A–B–A type polymers P1–P3 and B–A–B type polymers P4–P5 where A and B stand for PEO and PFPAE respectively, the results suggest that the average particle sizes increases with the increase of polymer molecular weights. Control of cmc is determined by placement of the PEO or the size of the PFPAE (**Table 15**) [136].

Table 15 : Micelle size and cmc characterization (adapted from RSC Adv. 2015;5:64170-64179) [136].

Polymer	Size (nm)	cmc (mg mL ⁻¹)
P1: PEG₁₀₀₀-PFPAE₄₀₀-PEG₁₀₀₀	100.5±74.2	0.014
P2: PEG₁₀₀₀-PFPAE₂₅₀₀-PEG₁₀₀₀	174.0±117.2	0.012
P3: PEG₂₀₀₀-PFPAE₂₅₀₀-PEG₂₀₀₀	209.9±120.6	0.011
P4: PFPAE₄₀₀-PEG₁₀₀₀-PFPAE₄₀₀	241.8±173.6	0.010
P5: PFPAE₃₇₄₅-PEG₁₀₀₀-PFPAE₃₇₄₅	255.5±117.3	0.101

PEOylated surfaces are known to be resistant to protein adsorption, which then should inhibit the adhesion and colonization of cells on the coated surfaces [136]. Increased chain length of the hydrophilic PEO segments in P1–P3 were tested and enhanced fouling resistance was evident [136]. It was discovered that the PFPAE and PEG together was a rational strategy to achieve high performance antibacterial coating materials. **Figure 24** clearly evidences the absence of *E. coli* and *S. aureus* on coated polymer compared to the silicon surface.

Fig. 24. Average settlement of *E. coli* and *S. aureus* on coated polymer surface with Si substrates [136]. Copyright 2015, Reproduced with permission from Royal Society of Chemistry.

In a fourth biological application [150], PFPAEs can be used to decrease multidrug resistance. It is known that block copolymers are able to reverse multidrug resistance (MDR) of tumor cells by a yet unknown mechanism. There are two main hypotheses for what causes MDR reversal as well as damage to the membrane barrier: 1) the direct and indirect inhibitions of the drug efflux system is mediated by polymer P-glycoprotein (Pgp) interactions or 2) adenosine triphosphate (ATP) depletion. To test the former hypothesis, the authors monitored the cellular drug accumulation in the presence of both overexpressed fluorescently labeled Pgp and different PEO-*b*-PHFPO-*b*-PEO triblock copolymers. Its administration induced drug uptake, whereas control cells with high Pgp expression levels

showed no drug accumulation. A TEM image of the triblock copolymer and its interpretation is given in **Figure 25**.

Fig. 25. TEM image of a $\text{PEO}_{2000}\text{-}b\text{-PHFPO}_{1100}\text{-}b\text{-PEO}_{2000}$ triblock copolymer after transferring on a carbon film. The dark contrast arises from fluorinated moieties with higher electron density (Left). Schematic presentation of elongated entities of amphiphilic triblock copolymers (Right) [150]. Copyright 2008, Reproduced with permission from ACS Publications.

7.2 Aerospace Materials

Originally developed in the early 1960's, PFPAs have been widely used as high-performance lubricants for aerospace and industrial applications because of their excellent tribological properties [2]. Only recently has there been an expanding interest in using PFPAs as aerospace elastomers which is evident by the assigned patents to 3M [103] and Labinal Power Systems (Safran) [146,151]. Fluoroelastomers are widely used in the industry because they preserve their elastomeric properties over a wide temperature range. In some applications, materials may be exposed to temperatures below $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ or even below $-100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for an extended period of time [3]. In addition, fluoroelastomers have high resistances to heat, chemicals and fuels. For example, fluoroelastomers are used in the automotive or aircraft industry and in chemical processing where resistance to fuel is required.

Presently, further challenges deal with the crosslinking of such fluoroelastomers to enhance their mechanical, thermal, and chemical stabilities. The 3M Company in their patent [103] claimed the crosslinking of telechelic PFPAs bis(iodo), bis(cyano) and bis(acrylate) via various strategies including the long and tricky synthesis of I-PFPAE-I in five

steps from HOCH₂-PFPE-CH₂OH. The inventors could obtain fluoroelastomers endowed with quite low T_g (ranging from -113 to -110 °C), even after crosslinking with a trifunctional agent.

Other routes for crosslinking include azide-alkyne Huisgen cycloaddition or “click” chemistry of alkynes and azides [104], also mentioned in section 6.3.2 (**Scheme 30**), the desired goal was to achieve elastomeric materials for both high and low temperatures. The kinetic rheology was reported on the cross-linked materials at 120 °C [152]. **Figure 26** exhibits the evolutions of G' and G'' moduli versus time for various telechelic alkynes and azides including pentaerythritol triazide as the cross-linking agent. F1-F6 were materials obtained from various formulations containing both the telechelic reactants and the trifunctional azido cross-linker with decreasing content, from 7.2% for F1 to 0% for F6.

Fig. 26. Kinetic rheological analyses of F1-F6 reactive mixtures at $T = 120\text{ °C}$ with G' storage (solid line) and G'' loss (dashed line) moduli [152]. Copyright 2017, Reproduced with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd.

The crosslinking time was determined from the intersection of both G' and G'' moduli curves and, as expected, the higher the crosslinking agent amount, the shorter the cross-linking time. **Figure 27** displays the pictures regarding various materials obtained according to the degree of cross-linking [152]. If 100% of the cross-linkages comes from pentaerythritol triazide (C3) with the telechelic bis(propargyl) PFPAE, F1 was formed. If 60% of the triazide cross-linkers comes from the reaction between telechelic bis(propargyl) and

bis(azide) PFPAEs, the other 40% comes from pentaerythritol triazide, F4 is produced. F6 was obtained from 100% triazide cross-linker between telechelic bis(propargyl) and bis(azide) PFPAEs. Therefore, the material arising from F1 can be used as O-ring or shaft seal while that originating from F6 could be employed as potting gel.

Fig. 27. Pictures of materials obtained from formulations F1 (left), F4 (middle, stuck on a PTFE sheet), and F6 (right) ranging with various states of crosslinked networks [152]. Copyright 2017, Reproduced with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd.

The thermostability of the materials arising from formulations F1-F6 was also investigated by thermogravimetric analyses under air. With a usual heating rate of $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ and in all cases, the onset of degradation was *ca.* $275\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at which a weight loss of *ca.* 2% was achieved [152]. Examples of temperature performances of the resulting cross-linked network compared to those of the starting reactants are displayed in **Figure 28**.

Fig. 28. TGA thermograms under air of F1 formulated telechelic bis(propargyl), triazido derivative, and cross-linked network [151]. Copyright 2017, Reproduced with permission from World Intellectual Property Organization.

The glass transition temperatures of the different networks produced from F1-F6 formulations can be observed by DSC (**Figure 29**). Each DSC thermogram displays two T_g s (T_g #1 and T_g #2). T_g #1, gradually shifts toward a lower temperature with decreasing cross-linking agent in the composition ratio from F1 to F6 (from -80 to -25 °C). However, in all cases T_g #2 was observed at -105 °C which is a typical value for soft PFPAE segments in PFPAE-based networks based on telechelic PFPAE-diazide. The investigation of the cross-linking reaction by DSC confirmed the highly exothermic nature of the azide-alkyne cycloaddition reaction ($\Delta H = 230 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) [152].

Fig. 29. DSC thermograms for PFPAAE-based materials arising from various F1-F6 formulations [152] Copyright 2017, Reproduced with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd.

7.3. Microfluidic Devices

Microfluidic devices are ever increasing in their application in drug discovery, organic synthesis, etc. [153,154]. This is primarily due to the fact they are able to generate relatively pure products in high yields. One particularly important feature that a microfluidic device must have is the ability to be solvent-resistance. The reason is for targeting organic-phase reaction such as polymer syntheses, combinatorial chemistry reactions, and oligonucleotide syntheses.

For example, DeSimone's research group [126] reported a novel solvent-resistant microfluidic device fabricated from PFPE-based elastomers and compared contact angles of PDMS versus PFPAAE-based elastomers (telechelic PFPAAE-dimethacrylate (DMA)) and found the PFPAAE to be more resilient to organic solvents (

Table 16).

Although PDMS has been used in microfluidics, such as Sylgard® 184 (Dow Corning), cured thermally through a platinum-catalyzed hydrosylation reaction, they do have several disadvantages. The cure times can take up to 5 hours and the materials suffer greatly from swelling in most organic solvents. They showed that photocuring can be achieved in minutes rather than hours with PFPAAEs. Their work has potential to expand the field of microfluidics to many novel applications and the authors are currently exploring how to use the device in

DNA synthesis. PFPAE-based elastomers have come on the scene to make up for some of the deficiencies of PDMS.

Table 16 : Static contact angle in degrees (adapted from J Am Chem Soc. 2004;126(8):2322–2323) [128].

Elastomer	Water	Methanol	Toluene	Dichloromethane
PFPAE DMA	107	35	40	43
Sylgard® 184	101	22	Swell*	Swell*

*solvent which swelled the material, no accurate measurement could be achieved.

The authors also developed actuation valves mounted in way that it could be pressured with 1.75 bar . When a solution was present in the channel, valve actuation was easily observed (Figures 30 and 31).

Fig. 30. Device fabrication procedure. (1) A thin layer (20 μm) and a thick layer (5 mm) of PFPE DMA are partially cured. (2) The thick layer is peeled off its wafer, rotated 90°, and placed on top of the thin layer. The entire device is then fully cured to adhere the two layers together. (3) The device is peeled off the wafer [128] Copyright 2004, Reproduced with permission from ACS Publications.

Fig. 31. A) Top-down view of channels containing no solvent. The channels on the thin layer (fluid) run vertically, while those on the thick layer (air) run horizontally. (B) Thin-layer channel filled with dyed solution of acetonitrile, dichloromethane, and methanol. (C) Valve actuation

produced by introducing 1.75 bar of air into the thick-layer channel. Beneath each picture, a cartoon representation of the valve [126]. Copyright 2004, Reproduced with permission from ACS Publications.

De Marco *et al.* [155] reported the ability to use PFPAE-urethane dimethacrylates with 4% w/w of photoinitiator to fabricate sub-100-nm organic light-emitting fibers after crosslinking. They were able to show a superior control over spatial arrangement and diameter. The optically active nanofibers were around 60 nm in diameters and exhibited photoluminescence emission polarized along the axis (**Figure 32**). These materials can be used for nanophotonics, sensors, and lab-on-a-chip devices.

Fig. 32. Organic light-emitting optically active nanofiber [155]. Copyright 2008, Reproduced with permission from John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

Vitale *et al.* [156], demonstrated that telechelic bis(methacrylate) PFPAEs can be photocured to fabricate a microfluid device *via* direct photolithographic processes (**Figure 33**).

Fig. 33. Multi-inlet lab on a chip (LOC) with a passive micromixer based on a bare, straight microchannel integrating a “Y” inlet junction: this is a structure that is already used in a

DNA hybridization protocol [156]. Copyright 2013, Reproduced with permission from ACS Publications.

Using the mask-assisted photopolymerization techniques, telechelic bis(methacrylate) PFPAEs were synthesized and directly polymerized in the presence of a mask, avoiding the use of a master. They presented an ability to display a high level of control in transferring complex micropattern features with high density. For example, for cure times of ca. 5 minutes, they could minimally transfer as pattern size of 15 μm microstructures with an aspect ratio of at least up to 6.5 [156]. They also demonstrated they can seal the devices to withstand flow pressures up to 3.8 bar (**Figure 34**).

Fig. 34. (a) Optical image of the quartz mask used to select the energy dose. (b) Sketch of the homemade exposure setup. (c) Process flow for the optimized direct photolithographic process [156]. Copyright 2013, Reproduced with permission from ACS Publications.

The optimization in cure times required energy dose control and exposure time to ensure complete polymerization at 300 $\text{mJ}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ (**Figure 35**). Overall, these authors used the mask-assisted photopolymerization process to fabricate a complete lab-on-a-chip (LOC) for chemical synthesis applications with solvent-resistance. The specific chemical synthesis

demonstrated was the formation of benzopinacol via the photoreduction of benzophenone in isopropanol [156].

Fig. 35. Photopolymerization conversion curve for a 20- μm -thick methacrylic PFPE film [156]. Copyright 2013, Reproduced with permission from ACS Publications.

In another example, Bong *et al.* [157] reported the unique ability to synthesize anisotropic particles from nonpolar organic precursors with stable dispersion of the upconverted nanocrystals (UCNs). As an application example, the embedded macroparticles can be used as an application against counterfeiting. The stop flow lithography (SFL) device was built using the PFP AE SIFEL[®] X71-8115 produced by Shin-Etsu Co (**Figure 36**). These authors demonstrated that similar SFL performances could be obtained in both PFP AE and PDMS devices since the particles produced from both devices displayed negligible differences in shapes and sharpness of interfaces of striped particles. Since PFP AEs exhibited a lower elastic modulus than that of PDMS, the PFP AE channels could extend lag times in the SFL process and decreased the particle throughput. In addition, they highlighted that PFP AE devices are completely compatible with organic solvents, allowing for the solvent-based SFL which can achieve particles with a higher degree of chemical complexity over PDMS-based SFL. Overall, the authors believe that SFL is a route to form multifunctional particles from organic precursors.

Fig. 36. Stop Flow Lithography (SFL) in a PFPAE device. (a) A schematic depicting the synthesis of triangular particles (b) top view of the process and bright-field and fluorescent images show particles synthesized in (a). (c) Synthesis of multifunctional barcoded particles. Bright-field and fluorescent images show the barcoded particles with three distinct compartments. The inserted image shows a code region of the barcoded particles with code “2013”. Scale bars are 100 μm (b) and 70 μm (c) [157]. Copyright 2014, Reproduced with permission from Royal Society of Chemistry.

7.4 Low Surface Tension, Anti-Fouling, and De-icing Coatings

To mitigate CaSO_4 deposits formation on metal surfaces (i.e. stainless steel AISI 316), Oldani *et al.* [158] reported that a hybrid coating prepared using a commercially available telechelic bis(triethoxysilane) PFPAE (Fluorolink®S10) in combination with tetraethoxysilane (TEOS) reduced surface deposits. The coatings were prepared by sol-gel synthesis and deposited on stainless steel substrates by a dip-coating procedures (**Figure 37**).

Fig. 37. SEM images of hybrid coatings deposited on stainless steel plain substrates (a, b, d); in comparison with a Fluorolink®S10 coating (c). Specifications: TEOS/S10-30/70 (a); TEOS/S10-20/80 (b); Fluorolink®S10 coating deposited on a stainless steel substrate by analogue procedure to the hybrid coating (c); bulk structure of TEOS/S10-30/70 (d) [158]. Copyright 2016, Reproduced with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd.

The synergistic effect of the two opposite phases, Fluorolink® S10 and TEOS, produced a hydrophobic coatings with a contact angle (CA) ca. 140° (**Table 17**) and with high resistance to thermal or mechanical stresses induced in liquid media. The material maintained unaltered CA value after exposition for 43 days to a flux of a CaSO₄ solution at a flowrate of 0.15 m/s. The rate of formation of scale deposit was reduced by 97% with respect to an uncoated stainless steel surface (**Table 18**).

Table 17 : Profile features of the coatings and wettability properties of the hybrid coatings expressed in terms of static contact angle, surface free energy and hysteresis between the advancing and receding contact angle (adapted from J Fluorine Chem. 2016;188:43–49) [158].

Coating Type	Static CA [θ]	Advancing CA [θ]	Hysteresis [θ]	Ra [μm]	Thickness [μm]
None	67	-	-	0.5	-
Fluorolink® S10	147	146	6	0.7	3
TEOS/FLNK S10 50/50	140	136	7	1.6	11
TEOS/FLNK S10 30/70	140	135	6	1.3	14

TEOS/FLNK S10 20/80	146	131	23	0.8	4
------------------------	-----	-----	----	-----	---

Table 18 : Results of particulate fouling tests (adapted from J Fluorine Chem. 2016;188:43–49) [158].

Coating type	Time [days]	Fluid velocity [$\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$]	Fouling [$\text{mg}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\text{ h}^{-1}$]
None	15	0.15	5.5×10^{-5}
TEOS/S10-20/80	15	0.15	1.8×10^{-6}
TEOS/S10-20/80	43	0.16	1.2×10^{-6}

Messori *et al.* [159] studied the sol-gel process, but with a slightly different type of telechelic PFPAE, using $(\text{EtO})_3\text{Si-PCL-}b\text{-PFPAE-}b\text{-PCL-Si(OEt)}_3$ triblock copolymer, mixed with silica to form organic-inorganic hybrid coating by a sol-gel process. The sol-gel process demonstrated to be highly versatile and convenient for the preparation of very smooth, transparent, hydrophobic and oleophobic coatings, usable to modify different kinds of substrates. **Table 19** displays water and n-hexadecane contact angles of the resulting coatings. The materials were coded as TXxCL(x')Si in which $x = 1, 2, 3$ denotes the average molecular weight of PFPAE (1190, 2200 or 3100 g mol^{-1} , respectively) while x' represents the number-average degree of polymerization of the short PCL segments in the copolymer.

Table 19 : Static contact angles with water ($\theta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$) and n-hexadecane (θ_{HEXA}) and total surface tension (γ) for hybrids applied by spin-coating and dip-coating (t_r : reaction time of the sol-gel process before coating application) (adapted from Progress in Organic Coatings. 2011;72:461–468) [159].

Material Code	Organic content (wt%) ^a	Coating application method	$t_r = 3\text{ h}$		$t_r = 1\text{ h}$		$\gamma(\text{mN m}^{-1})^b$
			$\theta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} (^{\circ})$	$\theta_{\text{HEXA}} (^{\circ})$	$\theta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} (^{\circ})$	$\theta_{\text{HEXA}} (^{\circ})$	
TX2CL(2)Si/SiO ₂ 5:95	5 (3.5)	Dip	105	63	-	-	-
		Spin	74	55	110	67	13.2 (1.3)
TX2CL(2)Si/SiO ₂ 10:90	10 (7.0)	Dip	105	64	-	-	-
		Spin	76	59	108	66	13.5 (1.6)
TX2CL(2)Si/SiO ₂ 20:80	20 (14.1)	Dip	106	67	-	-	-
		Spin	81	62	109	67	13.2 (1.5)
TX2CL(5)Si/SiO ₂ 5:95	5 (2.8)	Dip	104	61	-	-	-
		Spin	77	56	108	66	14.6 (2.4)
TX2CL(5)Si/SiO ₂ 10:90	10 (5.6)	Dip	105	65	-	-	-
		Spin	-	-	107	66	14.7 (2.4)
TX2CL(5)Si/SiO ₂ 20:80	20 (11.3)	Dip	100	67	-	-	-
		Spin	83	63	107	67	15.5 (2.9)
PCLSi/SiO ₂ 20:80	20 (0)	Dip	61	27	-	-	-
SiO ₂ from TEOS	0 (0)	Dip	57	24	-	-	42.5 (19.9)
Glass substrate	0 (0)	-	37	13	-	-	-

^a In bracket the PFPAE content (without the PCL contribution).

^b In bracket the polar component (γ^p) of the total surface tension

Since ice accumulation has an enormous impact on transportation (i.e. roads, boats, airplanes) and energy production (e.g., energy losses of wind turbines due to icing), a variety of so-called “icephobic” coatings and paints are commercially available. Using the sol–gel process, Susoof *et al.* [160] evaluated a new class of icephobic coatings by using silica precursors consisting of TEOS and/or (3-glycidylpropyl)trimethoxy silane (GPTMS) in combination with different ratios of telechelic PFPAE derived from Fluorolink®S10 ~2000 g/mol and with the following structure:

This material was tested as a coating and measured for ice adhesion shear stress using a frozen-in pin test. (**Figure 38**). When coatings consisting only of Fluorolink®S10 (sol–gel fluorinated 1a–c) (**Figure 39**) were produced, the lowest ice adhesion were observed [160]. The adhesion-reduction-factor (ARF)-value is about 20, which means that the adhesion of ice to these coatings is 20 times lower than that to bare aluminium. The static contact angle of water on this coating of nearly 120° evidences the hydrophobic behaviour. However, by incorporating fumed silica particles (Aerosil R805) to the coatings containing Fluorolink®S10, even more hydrophobic surfaces are obtained due to its structured and low energy surface. Moreover, these coatings “sol–gel fluorinated aerosil 1d + e” with static contact angles of 134° and 169°, respectively, show an enormous increase in adhesive strength to ice, especially the superhydrophobic “sol–gel fluorinated Aerosil 1e” (static water contact angle: 169°). The shear stress exceeds the ice adhesion of aluminium by more than 50%. Although this aspect was only analyzed for one single type of coating, it indicates the use of superhydrophobic coatings as potentially ice-phobic surfaces [160].

Fig. 38. Ice adhesion test setup. Left: adjustment of mould and corresponding frozen-in pin at tensile testing machine; right: sketch of the ice adhesion test setup [160]. Copyright 2013, Reproduced with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd.

Fig. 39. Screening of different coatings. Shear stress of investigated coatings that are classified into certain groups; horizontal line denotes mean shear stress of bare aluminium (referenced material), dotted line = standard deviation; shear stress value of Wearlon® was calculated [160]. Copyright 2014, Reproduced with permission from Elsevier Science Ltd.

Other forms of surfaces with superhydrophobicity, low contact angle hysteresis, and self-cleaning was demonstrated by DeSimone’s research team [161]. They prepared lotus-leaf-like topography materials (Figure 40) achieved by forming nanopillar structure using cross-linked styrene end-functionalized PFPAE and a highly fluorinated styrene sulfonate (SS)

(Scheme 22). The PFPE-SS nanopillars were measured to have lengths of $\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$ deposited on either flat or microdimples punctuated surfaces. The dynamic and static contact angles listed in

Table 20 reached 173° highlighting superhydrophobic coatings.

Table 20 : Dynamic and Static Water Contact Angles Measured on a Flat PFP AE-SS(styrenesulfonate) Surface, PFP AE-SS Nanopillars Fabricated Using a Flat p-AAO Membrane Anodized for 20 min and a PFP AE-SS Lotus-Leaf-like Structure (adapted from Langmuir. 2006;22(20):8576–8580)[161].

	Advancing contact angle (θ)	Receding contact angle (θ)	Max static contact angle (θ)	Tilted angle at which the water droplet begins rolling (θ)
PFP AE-SS Flat surface	107	73	104	
PFP AE-SS Nanopillars	173	162	171	3
PFP AE-SS Lotus leaf-like structure	170	160	169	3

Fig. 40. (A) Top view and (B) 30° angle oblique view FE-SEM images of a p-AAO membrane template anodized for 20 min at 180 V. (C) FE-SEM image of a PFP AE-SS nanopillar film peeled from

the p-AAO membrane. The inset is a water droplet sitting on the PFPE-SS nanopillars [161]. Copyright 2006, Reproduced with permission from ACS Publications.

When developing other types of superhydrophobic materials, which may not necessarily utilize telechelic PFPAEs, some teams have been inspired by the Nepenthes pitcher plant. For example, Wong *et al.* [162] have developed slippery liquid-infused porous surfaces (SLIPS™). The first examples of SLIPS were achieved by infusing perfluorinated liquids (e.g., Fluorinert™ FC-70, Krytox® 100 and 103) into two types of porous solids, periodically ordered epoxy-based nanostructured surfaces and random network of Teflon® nanofibrous membranes. The same team also were able to infuse a fluorogel made with PFPAE with fluorinated lubricants and they showed excellent anti-biofouling behavior while maintaining cytocompatibility and resistance to wetting by various liquids [163]. Manna *et al.* [164] reported nonfluorinated versions of SLIPS that are nanoporous and superhydrophobic polymer. In addition, Urata *et al.* [165] developed self-lubricating organogels (SLUGS) obtained from poly(ethyleneimine) (PEI) and poly(2-vinyl-4,4-dimethylazlactone) (PVDMA). Hence, there is clearly an opportunity to utilizing telechelic PFPAEs in the areas of SLIPS and SLUGS technologies.

7.5 Optically and Antireflective Transparent Films

Ko *et al.* [166] fabricated 3D microlens arrays using naturally occurring biological structures, such as a moth's eye (**Figure 41**). To prepare the curing mixtures, a telechelic urethane methacrylate PFPAE was utilized (Fluorolink® MD 700). The fidelity of a replication and the ability to tailor microlens arrays of variable materials, sizes, shapes, and curvatures through this simple extension of biomimicry, gave the surfaces unique properties.

Fig. 41. Scanning Electron Micrographs of (a) the *Attacus atlas* moth eye; (b) the PFPAE mould of the *Attacus atlas* moth eye; (c) a compound eye PU replica made by photopolymerizing the PU monomer in the PFPAE mould. The inset of (c) shows the curved surfaces of the replica. The scale bars are respectively 100 μm for the top images (inset: 20 μm), 5 μm for the second row images, and 500 nm for the third and fourth row images [166]. Copyright 2011, Reproduced with permission from Royal Society of Chemistry.

The combined advantages of anti-reflectivity (**Figure 42**) with hydrophobicity (**Figure 43**) afforded by the multiscale micro- and nanopatterns became apparent to the authors. Compared to other methods of fabricating curved microlens arrays, this curing method was very simple. The authors claimed that advantages of nonplanar compound microlens arrays produced with their methodology could be readily integrated into applications as photovoltaics, optical sensors, and optoelectronic devices.

Fig. 42. Moth eye reflectivity and hierarchical surface structure. (a) Measured reflectivity for unpolarized light at normal incidence for a natural moth eye, its PFPAE replica, a flat PU substrate, and an optical calculation. (b and c) SEM images of the replica. The parabolic protrusions result in broadband, anti-reflection. The scale bars are, respectively, 30 μm for

(b) and 500 nm for (c) [166]. Copyright 2011, Reproduced with permission from Royal Society of Chemistry.

Fig. 43. Images of a water droplet on (a) a flat PU substrate, (b) a PU smooth sphere, and (c) the PU moth eye replica. The same PFP AE mould used for the moth eye replica (d) is re-used to generate (e); identical dimension and feature shapes are derived from the second use of the PFP AE mould. Scale bars in (d) and (e) are 500 nm [166]. Copyright 2011, Reproduced with permission from Royal Society of Chemistry.

7.6 Self-Healing Materials

Limited work has been done on self-healing fluoropolymers, especially on PFP AEs. However, Li *et. al.* [117] could produce such materials via the presence of hydrogen bonding in uriedo-pyrimidinone (UPy) linkers (**Scheme 12**). They were highlighted by IR where the hydrogen bonded N-H stretches are evidenced at 3410 and 3320 cm^{-1} , for UPy end-groups. The comparative study indicated that PFPE-UPy chains exhibited lower mobility and required longer times to achieve full hydrogen bonding of available sites when annealed at $T = 130\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Conversely, PFPE-UPy-Bn is more rapidly engaged in complete hydrogen bonding at lower annealing temperatures at $110\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (**Figure 44**).

Fig. 44. FTIR of PFPE-UPy (a, c) and PFPE-UPy-Bn (b, d) in the 2300–3600 cm^{-1} region [117]. Copyright 2013, Reproduced with permission from John Wiley & Sons.

Regarding the thermal properties of such PFPAE-UPy, two endotherms are noted at 149.6 and 170.0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ even after repetitive thermal cycles. These transitions were assigned to crystallization and melting, respectively. These domains were associated with the UPy units, potentially serving as hard segments in the self-assembled polymeric material. Also, during cooling cycles, an exothermic transition was observed at 92 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Conversely, DSC thermograms of PFPE-UPy-benzyl (Bn) displayed one endothermic melting transition at 111 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ on the first heating, which progressively decreased with repeated thermal cycles. The comparative studies revealed that UPy end groups form hydrogen bonds readily, which further increases the driving force to crystallization of PFPE-UPy. Conversely, the benzylic moieties in PFPE-UPy-Bn suppresses both hydrogen bonding and crystallization. This correlation was also demonstrated by a higher melting point for of PFPE-UPy ($T_m = 170^{\circ}\text{C}$), in comparison to that of PFPE-UPy-Bn ($T_m = 110^{\circ}\text{C}$). In addition, several self-healing cycles measurements with PFPE-UPy confirmed rapid (2 min) and repeatable self-healing capability. Interestingly, stiffening was observed with repeated self-healing cycles which pointed to increased hydrogen bonding over time and subsequent enhancement of the shear storage modulus [117] (**Figure 45**).

Fig. 45. Multiple deformation-recovery cycles of PFPE-UPy (a) and PFPE-UPy-Bn (b) [117]. Copyright 2013, Reproduced with permission from John Wiley & Sons.

The dynamic moduli (G') and loss modulus (G'') were also conducted for both PFPE-UPy and PFPE-UPy-Bn. The oscillatory frequencies ranged from 0.1 to 100 rad s^{-1} under 0.1% of strain at 130 and 110 $^\circ\text{C}$, respectively (Figure 46). It was noted that gel-like properties occur when G' is larger than G'' and reasonably independent of frequency, like PFPE-UPy. However, if G' and G'' both decreased with decreasing frequency as in PFPE-UPy-Bn, indicating unstructured liquid or linear polymer behaviour [117].

Fig. 46. Frequency sweeps of PFPE-UPy (a) and PFPE-UPy-Bn (b)[117]. Copyright 2013, Reproduced with permission from John Wiley & Sons.

The self-healing behaviors were also confirmed by AFM [117]. **Figure 47** displays a dark continuous phase representing the PFPAE moieties whereas a light hard domain originated from the aggregated UPy moieties.

Fig. 47. AFM image of PFPE-UPy supramolecular polymer submonolayer islands spin-coated on Si-substrates exhibiting microphase separated morphology with domains of associated UPy units in a continuous phase of PFPAE [117]. Copyright 2013, Reproduced with permission from John Wiley & Sons.

7.7 Thermoplastic Elastomers

Tonelli *et al.* [49] developed a series of thermoplastic elastomers using Fomblin[®] ZDOL TX and diisocyanates as the primary linker between the alcohol groups (**Scheme 1**). The resulting polymers exhibit soft and hard segments assigned to PFPAE and alkyl groups from diisocyanate adducts, respectively. Tables 21-23 list physical characteristics of various PFPAE thermoplastic elastomers. They were further characterized by DSC, DMA, tensile stability, and tensiometry.

Table 21 displays the T_g s which are approximately -120 °C for all polymers containing PFPAEs, melt temperatures (T_m s) of the hard phase also trended to be higher with PFPAEs. Interesting mechanical properties are also observed.

Table 22 lists their tensile strength, whereas **Table 23** provides contact angles of common organic solvents on PFPAE-based and hydrocarbon-based polymers. As an additional application to explore, these PFPAE based thermoplastic elastomers would be interesting to test for their blood compatibility [167].

Table 21 : T_g , T_m , T_c , and enthalpies of melting assessed by DSC measurements of thermoplastic elastomers of polyurethanes based on PFPAEs (adapted from J Appl Polym Sci. 1996;59(2):311–327) [49].

Samples	T_g (°C)	Highest		Highest Second Melting		ΔH^a (Cal/g)
		T_m (°C)	T_c (°C)	T (°C)	T (°C)	
FB-1750-21	-120	216	105	170	170	1.0
FB-1750-29	-120	216	105	181	181	1.7
FB-1750-33	-120	218	105	186	186	2.2
PTB-1000-20	-70	108	51	132	132	2.6
PTB-1000-24	-70	188	77	145	145	3.5
PTB-1000-28	-70	183	79	155	155	4.2
FQ-1600-26	-120	245	120-210	245	245	2.5 ^b
FQ-1600-31	-120	247	116-210	246	246	2.6 ^b
FQ-1600-36	-120	245	119-213-227	247	247	2.9 ^b
PCB-1000-22	-40	79	/	/	/	1.7
PCB-1000-30	-40	187	48	145	145	1.6
PCB-1000-37	-38	180	81	164	164	2.7
PCB-1000-43	-38	182	90	174	174	3.5
PCQ-1000-31	-46	186	74	180	180	/

^a Calculated over all the melting peaks.

^b Underestimated.

The designation FB and FQ by the authors are used to indicate the ZDOLTX/MDI/BDO and ZDOLTX/MDI/HQE systems, respectively (methylene diphenyl 4,4'-diisocyanate=MDI ; 1,4-butandiol = BDO). PTB and PCB stand for the PTMEG/MDI/BDO and PCL/MDI/MDO systems, respectively (polytetramethyleneglycol=PTMEG, poly(caprolactone)diol=PCL, 2,2'-(1,4-phenylenedioxy)diethanol). PCQ designation indicates the PCL/MDI/HQE polymer. The two numbers after the designation represent soft segment followed by hard segment equivalent weight of the polymer. (reproduced with permission from J Appl Polym Sci. 1996;59(2):311–327)[49].

Table 22 : Tensile Properties of FB, FQ, and PTB polyurethanes(adapted from J Appl Polym Sci. 1996;59(2):311–327) [49].

Samples	Room Temperature				100°C			
	M20% (MPa)	M100% (MPa)	T_b (MPa)	E_b (%)	M20% (MPa)	M100% (MPa)	T_b (MPa)	E_b (%)
PFPAE Based								
FB-1750-21	12.5	6.2	11.5	570	6.7	2.5	5.5	510
FB-1750-29	20.0	8.9	18.0	490	14.0	3.9	9.2	438
FB-1750-33	21.5	9.5	17.7	450	14.5	4.3	8.1	354
FQ-1600-26	22.6	7.8	11.0	290	12.5	4.4	5.8	220
FQ-1600-31	23.8	9.4	15.8	408	14.9	5.2	8.6	330
FQ-1600-36	26.0	10.2	15.0	303	15.5	5.5	7.7	250
Hydrogenated								
PTB-1000-20	6.5	3.1	42.0	492	5.2	2.2	3.9	320
PTB-1000-24	9.5	4.1	48.3	477	8.9	3.0	5.8	292
PTB-1000-28	13.3	5.5	49.3	480	14.8	4.8	9.1	310
PCB-1000-22	6.5	2.8	45.5	470	2.5	1.5	6.1	558
PCB-1000-30	13.2	5.0	58.0	450	9.0	3.1	6.3	314
PCB-1000-37	20.0	7.6	56.0	435	12.8	4.0	13.2	415
PCB-1000-43	27.2	9.6	52.0	425	15.5	5.0	20.5	456
PCQ-1000-31	18.0	6.4	46.3	565	12.0	4.0	13.4	822

Table 23 : Contact angles of PCB and FB polyurethanes (adapted from J Appl Polym Sci. 1996;59(2):311–327) [49].

Liquid	γ_{LC} (mN/m)	PCB-1000-30		FB-1750-29	
		$\bar{\theta}$	$\cos \bar{\theta}$	$\bar{\theta}$	$\cos \bar{\theta}$
Ethylene glycol	48.5	90.4	0.0065	76.7	0.230
1,4-Butanediol	45.2	82.6	0.128	72.3	0.304
DMSO	44.2	71.7	0.315	71.7	0.314
Methylformamide	41.5	64.2	0.435	65.3	0.418
2-chloroethanol	40.0	53.9	0.589	61.9	0.471
Pluronic 10R5	36.7	49.8	0.646	63.8	0.442
Acetic acid	27.8	/	/	46.3	0.691
2-propanol	21.7	/	/	32.9	0.840

7.8 Materials for Energy

New materials based on PFPAEs have also been designed for energy conversion and storage. For the first application, DeSimone *et al.* [111] developed a method to form polymer electrolyte membranes (PEMs) for fuel cells that are produced through UV photocuring of telechelic PFPAE and sulfonated styrene. These authors copolymerize a low molecular weight liquid precursor of telechelic bis(styrene) PFPAEs with a fluorinated styrene further hydrolyzed into a sulfonic acid styrene monomer that further led to a conductive solid membranes (**Scheme 22**). The curing process allows for direct control of its dimensions without the need for solvent casting or melt extrusion (**Figure 48**), while such a copolymerization tuned the content of the sulfonate group, hydrolyzing it into sulfonic acid function to bring conductivity to the membrane. High ionic exchange capacity of $1.50 \text{ meq}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ was reached. Their methodology for cross-linking enabled for the addition of a significant amount of acidic groups without causing the membrane to be water-soluble or swell significantly. Advantageously, the fabrication of membrane electrode assemblies (MEAs) from these PEMs resulted in fuel cells that outperformed those based on commercially available materials (Nafion® 117) reaching a power density of $225 \text{ mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$. The patterned membranes in MEAs demonstrated higher power densities over nonpattern membranes (**Figure 48**). In addition, photocuring (soft lithography) enabled three-dimensional patterning which provided a larger interfacial area between the catalysts and the membrane

in the PEMs. The patterning could potentially miniaturize fuel cells and promote their applications in portable devices.

Fig. 48. Left) SEM pictures of patterned membranes with feature dimensions $3 \times 3 \times 1.9 \mu\text{m}$, and membrane electrode assembly (MEA) performance of patterned and flat sPFPE-SS PEMs with an IEC value of 1.50 mequiv/g and thickness of $190 \mu\text{m}$ at $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and 75% RH; Right) Power Output Curves of such crosslinked PEMs [111]. Copyright 2006, Reproduced with permission from ACS Publications.

Another application of PFPAEs validated by the same research group deals with non-flammable electrolytes for LIBs [110]. Applications in grid storage or transportation can be difficult with conventional LIB since alkyl carbonate to dissolve lithium salts are flammable. It was discovered that bis(trifluoromethane)sulfonimide lithium salt along with telechelic bis(carbonate) PFPAEs led to an efficient non-flammable electrolyte system. These original compounds exhibit low T_g (**Figure 49**) and good thermal stability $> 200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (**Figure 50**) and a high unprecedented transference numbers of at least 0.91 (more than double that of conventional electrolytes) to form safer high-energy lithium batteries [110].

Fig. 49. PFPAE oligomers as Li-ion electrolytes. (A) Chemical reaction scheme describing the synthesis of PFPE-DMC from PFPE-diol. (B) PFPE-diol and PFPE-DMC electrolytes with corresponding degrees of polymerization and glass transition temperatures [110]. Copyright 2014, Reproduced with permission from United States National Academy of Sciences.

Cells of Li/LiNi_{1/3}Co_{1/3}Mn_{1/3}O₂ containing the new electrolyte exhibited galvanostatic cycling with good performance. Confirming their potential as rechargeable LIBs [110], these materials would enhance safety and longevity of LIBs and can be integrated seamlessly into current manufacturing infrastructure.

Fig. 50. Thermal stability and flammability of PFPEs. (A) TGA thermograms for thermal decompositions of DMC (solid gray), PFPAE₁₀₀₀-diol (dashed blue), and PFPAE₁₀₀₀-DMC (solid green). (B) Corresponding decomposition temperature (5%), sustained burning characteristics, and flash points of these [110]. Copyright 2014, Reproduced with permission from United States National Academy of Sciences.

Later, Balsara's [168] and DeSimone's groups [169] tested lithium LiTFSI with various telechelic PFPAEs bearing different end groups (diol, dimethyl carbonate,

ethoxy–diol, and ethoxy–dimethyl carbonate) as original electrolytes in LIBs (**Table 24**). The immiscibility of the salt was driven by the limited miscibility of the PFPAE and PEO, rather than the limit of LiTFSI solubility. Since connecting microscopic transport properties to a continuum-scale of such key characteristics would be helpful in generating rational design electrolytes improvements for applications in LIBS, the relationship between conductivity, ion diffusion, and transference number was established.

Table 24: PFPAEs with different end-groups for testing with electrolytes (adapted from *Macromolecules*. 2016;49 (9):3508–3515) [168].

Polymer	Structure	m	n	q	M_n [g·mol ⁻¹]
PFPAE _{D10} -Diol		7	3	0	1,188
PFPAE _{D10} -DMC		7	3	0	1269
PFPAE _{E10} -Diol		5	4	2	1,198
PFPAE _{E10} -DMC		5	4	2	1,314
PEO 5M		-	-	1.14E5	~5,015E3

The conductivity (**Figure 51, left**) and ion self-diffusivity (**Figure 51, right**) of these electrolytes were determined. Diffusivities, monitored by NMR, were the highest in PFPE_{D10}-DMC, while conductivity was maximized in PFPE_{E10}-Diol.

Fig. 51. Left) Ionic conductivities measured at 28 °C and 9.1 wt% salt loading (0.56 M for PFPE_{D10} and 0.57 M for PFPE_{E10}) are plotted for each PFPAE electrolyte. Ionic conductivities were averaged over three samples, and error bars represent the standard deviation of the measurements ; Right) Diffusivities of Li and TFSI ions, measured by 7Li and 19F NMR at 30 °C, are plotted for each PFPE electrolyte [168]. Copyright 2016, Reproduced with permission from ACS Publications.

7.9 Resistant Photoresists for Lithographic Materials

Photoresists are light-sensitive materials that can be used to form patterned coatings on a surface. One example based on PFPAEs was suggested by Gilles *et al.* [170]. They utilized telechelic urethane bis(methacrylate) PFPAE (Fluorolink® MD 700) with benzoin methyl ether (BME; PI) as the photoinitiator and pentaerythritol triacetate (PETA; CL) as cross-linking agent. In a stepwise fashion, the authors first created silicon-based primary masters fabricated with e-beam lithography and reactive ion etching. The etched trenches were measured at 108 nm in depth. 1H,1H,2H,2H-Perfluorooctyltrichlorosilane was then applied as releasing agent. Next, the UV-based replica mold was produced by drop-casting the telechelic PFPAEs onto the silicon master and then exposed to UV light ($\lambda = 365$ nm). Finally, the UV imprint was accomplished with a two-layer resist system NXR-3020 and NXR-2010 (Figures 52 and 53). An example of the width of the master, mold, and imprint is provided in

Table 25.

Fig. 52. Schematic representation of soft NIL process with (a) master, (b) mold and (c) imprint [170]. Copyright 2010, Reproduced with permission from IOP Publishing.

Fig. 53. Top) SEM image of (a) master and (b) imprint with design 1, scale bars 200 nm. Bottom) AFM images of corresponding (a) master, (b) mold and (c) imprint [170]. Copyright 2010, Reproduced with permission from IOP Publishing.

PFPAAE stamps of different compositions were suitable for replication of nanostructures by means of UV-NIL. However, if the pressure applied to the stamp was too high, deformation took place. Deformation was primarily due to the structure size. The relative deformation increases with decreasing structure width.

Table 25 : Comparison of original trench width and imprinted trench width with design 1 (adapted from Nanotechnology. 2010;21:245307) [170].

	$w(1)$ (nm)	$w(2)$ (nm)	$w(3)$ (nm)	$w(4)$ (nm)	$w(5)$ (nm)
Master	146 ± 7	95 ± 3	72 ± 6	96 ± 4	143 ± 4

PFPAE mold	155±5	94±8	80±7	93±6	137±5
Imprint with standard PFPAE	202±5	149±6	124±6	148±6	197±9

In a similar function for the PFPAEs, Kelly and DeSimone [171] found an application to conduct nano-molding for protein particles. They fabricated proteins of monodisperse size and shape. Using PRINT technology, the authors were able to produce monodisperse particles of 100% protein in any shape or size (as small as 200 nm cylinders) (illustrated in **Figure 54** and SEM in **Figure 55**). Their research demonstrated the used of Abraxane® in their process, which is the gold standard therapeutic drug for metastatic breast cancer.

Fig. 54. Illustration of PRINT nano-molding of protein particles. Silicon master template (A); mold (green) release from master template (B); nano-molding via capillary fill (protein solution red) with countersheet having a higher surface energy than the PFPE mold (C); filled mold lyophilized (D); glass slide (blue) with harvest film (yellow) (E); filled mold rolled onto harvest film (F); mold release from array of isolated features (G); dissolution of the harvesting film (H).

to yield free particles (H) [171]. Copyright 2008, Reproduced with permission from ACS Publications.

In order to accomplish this task of nano-molding, the photochemically curable telechelic PFPAE was first deposited onto the silicon patterned master templates and cured. The nano-molding of the protein was achieved by placing aqueous protein solution between the patterned PFPAE mold and a polyethylene (PE), poly(cyano acrylate) or a poly(vinyl pyrrolidinone) sheet. The PFPAE mold, aqueous protein solution and sheet sandwich was passed through a roller while peeling away the sheet afterwards. The filled mold was subsequently frozen and lyophilized overnight to remove the water and then harvested.

Fig. 55. SEM micrographs of the PRINT process. (A) SEM micrograph of an etched silicon master template of 200 nm posts; (B) cured PFPAE mold of the master template shown in A; (C) 200 nm albumin particles harvested on a (poly(vinyl pyrrolidinone) sheet; (D) etched silicon master template of 2 μm cubes, aspect ratio 2; (E) cured PFPAE mold of the master template shown in D; 2 μm insulin particles harvested on (poly(vinyl pyrrolidinone) sheet; (G) etched silicon master template of 5 μm cubes, aspect ratio 1; (H) cured PFPAE mold of the master template shown in G; (I) 5 μm albumin cubes harvested on (poly(vinyl pyrrolidinone) sheet; (J) 200 nm Abraxane® particles harvested on medical adhesive; (K) 200 nm albumin with siRNA particles harvested onto medical adhesive; (L) harvested and dispersed 200 nm albumin particles [171]. Copyright 2008, Reproduced with permission from ACS Publications.

Lastly, De Marco *et al.* [172] demonstrated femtosecond laser nanofabrication as well as using an original PFPAE resin bearing six acrylate functions [133], were able to produce new photoresists which could be employed for manufacturing solvent-resistant microfluidic elements and hydrophobic AFM tips (**Figure 56**).

Fig. 56. SEM images of a $50\ \mu\text{m} \times 50\ \mu\text{m} \times 50\ \mu\text{m}$ woodpile structure of the PFPE-based resin obtained by two photon polymerization(2PP): (a) top view and (b) tilted (45°) view. The structure is fabricated at a speed of 1 mm/s with an average laser power of 3 mW [133]. Copyright 2013, Reproduced with permission from ACS Publications.

7.10 Theranostics

Intracellular pH measurements and in vivo cell tracking technologies using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) are discussed in this section.

Patrick *et al.* [120] reported the synthesis and formulation of unique telechelic PFPAE nanoemulsions enabling intracellular pH measurements in living cells via fluorescent microscopy and flow cytometry. The formulation of the nanoemulsion containing cyanine-based fluorescents (specifically Cy3-PFC and CypHer5-PFC) (**Scheme 15**) conjugates permitted them to readily enter cells upon co-incubation. The application of this study demonstrated by loading rat 9L glioma cells with nanoemulsion. The local pH of such nanoemulsions were longitudinally quantified using optical microscopy and flow cytometry (**Figure 57**).

Fig. 57. The spectral and pH-sensing properties of the nanoemulsions [120]. Copyright 2013, Reproduced with permission from ACS Publications.

The nanoemulsions were noted to be rapidly uptake into acidic compartments, most likely endosomes, within the cell. A decrease of pH to 5.5 over a 3 hour period was observed. Also, the polyamine-driven nanoemulsion uptake is likely driving the labeling in nonphagocytic cells. This demonstrated that real-time optical detection of intracellular pH in living cells in response to pharmacological manipulations was possible. The pH-sensing nanoemulsions allowed the study of the fate of the PFPAE nanoemulsion tracer inside the labeled cell, which is important for understanding the PFPAE nanoemulsion cell loading dynamics, nanoemulsion stability and cell viability.

Janjic *et al.* [95] and Ahrens *et al.* [173] published other interesting surveys on self-delivering nanoemulsions involving telechelic PFPAE for dual ^{19}F -MRI and fluorescence, while separate work for near infrared detection [174]. For example, Janjic *et al.* [95] reported the design and use of a highly stable, nontoxic PFPAE nanoemulsions. The linear telechelic PFPAE fluorescent dyes (i.e. dye is FITC, Alexa647 or BODIPy-TR) was emulsified by microfluidization. The resulting nanoemulsion of less than 200 nm was readily taken up by both phagocytic and nonphagocytic cells in vitro after 3 hours of co-incubation. Indeed, the ^{19}F MRI easily and selectively visualized cell migration (**Figure 58**). The fluorescence detections was observed in immune cell types including Jurkat cells, primary T cells and dendritic cells (DCs) [95]. The combination of detections system can be used to calibrate cell loading in vitro. It was found that ^{19}F T1 (437 ms) of linear PFPAE molecule was 2.2 shorter than the T1 at 11.7 Tesla of perfluoro-15-crown-5-ether and far less sensitive to coordinating with oxygen [95]. Therefore, T1 of linear PFPAE was less sensitive to oxygen unlike perfluoro-15-crown-5-ether. In the end, they demonstrated the dual mode reagent can efficiently label T cells and dendritic cells (DCs) in culture and is nontoxic.

Fig. 58. Left) Preparation of the Fluorescent PFPAE Nanoemulsions, Middle) fluorescence of the PFPAE nanoemulsion with the T cell, Right) In vivo MRI of labeled T cells in the mouse model Confocal image of labeled T cells showing cytoplasmic localization of nanoemulsion post-labeling (red) and the CD4-FITC labeled cell surface (green) [95]. Copyright 2008, Reproduced with permission from ACS Publications.

8. Conclusions and Perspectives

Telechelic PFPAEs are quite interesting reactants for a wide range of relevant further intermediates involved in many innovative materials for high tech applications. Though PFPAEs are expensive, due to their complex synthesis under photopolymerization of perfluoro-olefins in oxygen and their low production volume, they have reached industrial pilot scale. In 2008, Solvay Solexis expanded their commercialization of PFPAEs. As fluoropolymers, they are currently undergoing a global increase of production (ca. 5%). They can also be modified by conventional chemical reactions leading to original telechelics in which the end-groups range from iodo, cyano, tosyl, azido, ester, carbonate, alkyne (or propargyl), (meth)acrylate, or styrenic, etc. Hence, these difunctional intermediates open the way to polycondensation, thiol-ene, Huisgen (or “click”), (trans)esterification, photocross-linking reactions yielding a wide variety of linear (triblocks) or cross-linked materials.

However, there are limitations to obtain PFPAE macromonomers where their terminus functionality is identical. Without high purity of the end-groups, there is a lack of appropriate stoichiometry and, as a consequence, it creates lower average molecular weight materials. In addition, though a few block, graft and alternated multiblock copolymers bearing PFPAEs have been reported, their physical properties were not deeply studied. While well-designed architectures of PFPAEs (e.g. hyperbranched or dendrimers) deserve further investigations, the little work produced in this area thus far may be due to the lack of robust synthetic methods adapted to fluorinated copolymers.

Finally, this review provides several recent innovative achievements from such materials, such as self-assembly objects, aerospace materials, microfluidic devices, low surface tension, anti-fouling, and de-icing coatings, optically and anti-reflective transparent films, self-healing materials, thermoplastic elastomers, components for energy, resistant photoresists for lithographic materials, and theranostics. Interestingly, thanks to low T_g values brought by soft PFPAE segments, original polycondensates block copolymers, and cured networks will find more applications. Nevertheless, phase separation may occur but

can be used for valuable morphologies. Thus, it is expected that further problems will be solved and more advancements will be achieved while many academic and industrial researchers will devote more effort into this stimulative research area of PFPAs in the coming decades.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC), Chaire Total Fondation Balard, Horizon 2020-Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions: Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE), the French National Network (GIS) and French National Agency (ANR) for their financial contributions and Esther Anna Friesen (Fry) [19 June 1950 - 9 May 2017] for encouraging people to never give up but to do their very best even through adversity.

References

-
- [1] Slinn DS, Green SW. Fluorocarbon fluids for the use industry in the electronic industry in preparation, properties and industrial applications of organofluoride compounds. In: Banks REE, editor. Chichester: Ellis Horwood Ltd Publi; 1982.
 - [2] Scheirs J. Perfluoropolyethers (Synthesis, Characterization and Applications), in: J. Scheirs, (Ed.), *Modern Fluoropolymers*, Wiley Interscience, New York, 1997:435-485.
 - [3] Moore AL. *Fluoroelastomer Handbook; The Definitive User's Guide and Data Book* Norwich: William Andrew Publishing 2006.
 - [4] Mikes F, Teng H, Kostov G, Ameduri B, Koike Y, Okamoto Y. Synthesis and characterization of perfluoro-3-methylene-2,4-dioxabicyclo[3,3,0] octane: Homo- and copolymerization with fluorovinyl monomers. *J Polym Sci, Part A: Polym Chem.* 2009;47(23):6571-6578.
 - [5] Maynor B, Larue I, Hu Z, Rolland JP, Pandaya A, Fu Q, Spontak RJ, Sheiko SS, Samulski RJ, Samulski ET, DeSimone JM. Supramolecular nanomimetics, replication of micelles, viruses, and other naturally occurring nanoscale objects. *Small* 2007;3(5):845-849.
 - [6] Hu Z, Finlay JA, Chen L, Betts DE, Hillmyer MA, Callow ME, James A. Callow JA, DeSimone JM. Photochemically Cross-Linked Perfluoropolyether-Based Elastomers: Synthesis, Physical Characterization, and Biofouling Evaluation. *Macromolecules.* 2009;42(18):6999-7007.
 - [7] Cui Z, Drioli E, Lee YM. Recent progress in fluoropolymers for membranes. *Prog Polym Sci.* 2014;39(1):164-198.
 - [8] Wang Y, Betts DE, Finlay JA, Brewer L, Callow ME, Callow JA, Wendt DE, DeSimone JM. Photocurable Amphiphilic Perfluoropolyether/Poly(ethylene glycol) Networks for Fouling-Release Coatings. *Macromolecules.* 2011;44(4):878-885.
 - [9] Allen, G. *Comprehensive Polymer Science: The Synthesis, Characterization, Reactions & Applications of Polymers*, Second supplement. 1st Edition. Pergamon Press: Oxford, England; New York, USA; 1996:347-388.
 - [10] Améduri B, Boutevin B, Kostov G. Fluoroelastomers: synthesis, properties and applications. *Prog Polym Sci.* 2001;26(1):105-187.

-
- [11] S.V. Sokolov and I.G. Kolokol'tseva, *Polym. Sci. SerA*, 1996, 225-231 (translated from *Vysokomol. Soed.*1996;38: 400-406).
- [12] Hougham G, Cassidy PE, Johns K, Davidson J. *Fluoropolymers: Synthesis and Applications*. Plenum Publish: New York, USA ; 1999.
- [13] Ebnesajjad S. *Fluoroplastics Volume 2: Melt Processible Fluoropolymers The Definitive User's Guide and Databook*. Plastics Design Library: Norwich, New York, USA; 2003.
- [14] Ameduri B, Boutevin B. *Well Architected Fluoropolymers: Synthesis and Applications*. Elsevier:Amsterdam; 2004.
- [15] Boschet F, Ameduri B. (Co)polymers of Chlorotrifluoroethylene: Synthesis, Properties, and Applications. *Chem Rev.* 2014;114(2):927-980.
- [16] Lagow RJ, Bierschenk TR, Junkle TJ, H K. A new synthetic procedure for the preparation and the manufacture of perfluoroethers in synthetic fluorine chemistry. New-York: J Wiley & Sons Inc.; 1992.
- [17] Scicchitano M, Turri S. Cyclic acetals of fluorinated polyether macrodiols *J Fluorine Chem.* 1999;95:97-103.
- [18] Gilson R, Grundy PJ. Fluorine compoud lubrication of thin film mangnetic media In: Salford, editor. *Fluorine Coating I Conference*, Paint Research Association. UK28 30 September 1994.
- [19] Gelin MP, Ameduri B. Fluorinated block copolymers containing poly(vinylidene fluoride) or poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene) blocks from perfluoropolyethers: synthesis and thermal properties. *Journal of Polymer Science, Part A: Polymer Chemistry* 2002;41(1):160-171.
- [20] Avataneo M, De Patto U, Guarda PA, Marchionni G. Perfluoropolyether–tetrafluoroethylene (PFPE–TFE) block copolymers: An innovative family of fluorinated materials. *J Fluorine Chem.* 2011; 132(11):885-891.
- [21] Lapčík J, Gimello O, Ladmira V, Friesen CM, Ameduri B. A new oligo(hexafluoropropylene oxide)-b-oligo(ethylene oxide) diblock surfactant obtained by radical reactions. *Polymer Chemistry* 2015;6:79-96.
- [22] Wang W, Castner DG, Grainger DW. Ultrathin films of perfluoropolyether-grafted polysiloxanes chemisorbed via alkylthiolate anchors to gold surfaces. *Supramolecular Science* 1997;4 (1–2): 83-99.
- [23] Worm AT. Low temperature fluorocarbon elastomers. 2000 WO2000/012574 (assigned to Dyneon LLC).
- [24] Casazza E, Mariani A, Ricco L, Russo S. Synthesis, characterization, and properties of a novel acrylic terpolymer with pendant perfluoropolyether segments. *Polymer* 2002;43:1207-1214.
- [25] Gelin MP, Ameduri B. Synthesis of an original poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene)-g-perfluoropolyether graft copolymer. *Journal of Fluorine Chemisty* 2003 ; 119 : 53-58.
- [26] Friesen CM, Ameduri B. Radical Copolymerization of Vinylidene fluoride (VDF) with Oligo(Hexafluoropropylene oxide) perfluorovinyl Ether Macromonomer to Obtain PVDF-g-oligo(HFPO) Graft Copolymers. *Macromolecules* 2015, 48 (19), 7060–7070.
- [27] Lee YJ, Shin JG; Lee MJ, Kadovski D. Hyperbranched fluorinated polymers with controlled refractive index. *Repub. Korean Kongkae Taeho Kongbo* (2013),KR 2013-066940 A 20130621.
- [28] Zhu Z, Li Q, Zhang L, Chen M, Fan S. UV-based nanoimprinting lithography with a fluorinated flexible stamp. *Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology, B: Nanotechnology &*

Microelectronics: Materials, Processing, Measurement & Phenomena. 2011;29(2):021015/1-021015/6.

- [29] Haszeldine RN. The fluorination of acetonitrile, trifluoroacetonitrile, ethylamine, trifluoroethylamine, heptafluorobutyronitrile, heptafluorobutylamine and aliphatic ethers. *Research*;1951;4(7):338-339.
- [30] Sianesi D, Pasetti A, Corti C. Process for preparing perfluorinated linear polyethers. British Patent 1,104,482 (1968); 1972 US Patent 3,704,214 (assigned to Montedison).
- [31] Sianesi D, Fontanelli R. Perfluorinated Polyethers. 1972 British Patent 1,226,566 (assigned to Montedison).
- [32] Hill JT. Polymers from Hexafluoropropylene Oxide (HFPO). *J Macromolecular Sci: Part A - Chem* 1974 ;8(3): 499-520.
- [33] Ohasaka Y, Tozuka T, Takaki S. Halogen-containing polyether. 1989 US Patent 4,845,268 (assigned to Daikin Industries); Y. Ohsak, *Petrotech (Tokyo)* 8, 840 (1985).
- [34] Lagow RJ, Gerhardt GE. Method for forming perfluorocarbon ethers. 1985 US Patent 4,523,039 A (assigned to the University of Texas).
- [35] Chambers RD, Hutchinson J, Kelly NM, Joel AK, Rees AJ, Telford PT. Free radical chemistry. Part 9. Approaches to fluorinated polyethers-model compound studies. *Isr J Chem*. 1999;39:133-140.
- [36] Bierschenk TR, Kawa H, Junkle TJ, Lagow RJ. Perfluorination of polyethers prepared by polymerisation of acetals, ketals, and other esters. NASA Contract Report-1821551988.
- [37] Jones WR, Bierschenk TR, Junkle TJ, Kawa H, Lagow RJ. Preparation of new perfluoro ether fluids exhibiting excellent thermal-oxidative. *Ind Eng Chem Prod Res Rev*. 1988;27(8):1497-1502.
- [38] Lagow RJ, Inoue S. Method for producing perfluoroether oligomers having terminal carboxylic acid groups. 1975 US 4113772 A (assigned to Lagow).
- [39] Howell JL, Shtarov AB, Thrasher JS, Waterfeld A, Murata K, Friesen CM, Pérez EW. Synthesis of new linear perfluoroalkyl polyethers starting from diols and tetrafluoroethylene. *Lubrication Science* 2011; 23:61–80.
- [40] Fritz G, Moore P. Dicarboxylic Acids of Fluorocarbon Ethers and Fluorides, Esters, Amides and Salts Thereof. 1966 US Patent 3,250,807.
- [41] Hill JT, Erdman JP. Anionic Polymerization of Fluorocarbon Epoxides. Ring-Opening Polymerization. American Chemical Society, 1977; 59: 19–269. ACS Symposium Series.
- [42] Ding JF, Proudmore M, Mobbs RH, Khan AR, Price C, Booth, C. Controlled synthesis of α,β -difunctional poly(hexafluoropropylene oxide). *Die Makromolekulare Chemie*. 1992 ; 193(9) : 2211–2219.
- [43] Resnick PR. Dialkyl Perfluoro- ω -Fluoroformyl Diesters and Monomers and Polymers Therefrom. 1982 US Patent 4334082 A, (assigned to DuPont).
- [44] Resnick PR. Alkyl- ω -Fluoroformyl Ester and Process. 1983 US Patent 4,390,720 A (assigned to DuPont).
- [45] Caporiccio G, Viola G, Corti C. Pefluoropolyethers, and a process for the preparation of the same. 1983 Eur. Pat. 89,820 (assigned to Montedison).
- [46] Tanesi D, Pasetti A, Corti C. Fluorinated oxygen containing acyl fluorides. 1969 US Patent 3,442,942 (assigned to Montefluos).
- [47] Sianesi D, Marchionni G, De Pasquale RJ. Perfluoropolyethers, in *Organofluorine Chemistry: Principles and Commercial Applications*; Banks, R. E., Smart, B. E., Tatlow, J. C., Eds.; Plenum Press: New York, 1994:431.

-
- [48] Marchionni G, Ajroldi G, Staccione AM, Dardani P, Pezzin G. Synthesis and characterization of perfluoropolyethers from perfluoromethylvinylether. *J Fluorine Chem.* 1999;95:85-95.
- [49] Tonelli C, Trombetta T, Scicchitano M, Simeone G, Ajroldi G. New fluorinated thermoplastic elastomers. *J Appl Polym Sci.* 1996;59(2):311–327.
- [50] Turri S, Scicchitano M, Tonelli C. End group chemistry of fluoro-oligomers: Highly selective syntheses of diepoxy, diallyl, and tetraol derivatives. *J Polym Sci, Part A: Polym Chem.* 1996;34(16):3263-3275.
- [51] Sianesi D, Pasetti A, Fontanelli R, Bernardi GC, Caporiccio G. Perfluoropolyethers by photooxidation of fluoroolefins. *Chim. Ind.* 1973;55:208.
- [52] Fautitano A, Buttafava A, Comincioli V, Marchionni G, De Pasquale RJ. Kinetic modelling of the low-temperature photo-oxidation of hexafluoropropene. *J Phys Org Chem* 1991;4: 293.
- [53] Bunyard WC, Romack TJ, DeSimone JM. Perfluoropolyether Synthesis in Liquid Carbon Dioxide by Hexafluoropropylene Photooxidation. *Macromolecules* 1999; 32: 8224-8226.
- [54] Guarda PA, Marchionni G. Process for preparing peroxidic perfluoropolyethers. 1998 US Patent 5,783,789 and 1998 US Patent 5,777,291. (assigned to Ausimont).
- [55] Turri S, Scicchitano M, Simeone G, Tonelli C. Chemical approaches toward the definition of new high-solid and high-performance fluorocoatings. *Prog Org Coat* 1997; 32: 205.
- [56] Ciampelli F, Venturi MT, Sianesi D. The ¹⁹F chemical shift in oxygen containing carbon fluorine products. *Org Magn Reson* 1969;1:281.
- [57] Pianca M, del Fanti N, Barchiesi E, Marchionni G. Characterization of perfluoropolyethers. *Chimica Oggi-Chem Today* 1995;13(1-2):29-46.
- [58] Karis TE, Marchon B, Hopper DA, Siemens RL. Perfluoropolyether characterization by nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy and gel permeation chromatography *J Fluorine Chem* 2002;118: 81-94.
- [59] Tonelli C, Gavezotti P, Strepparola E. Linear perfluoroether difunctional oligomers chemistry, properties and applications. *J Fluorine Chem.* 1999;95:51-70.
- [60] Guarda PA, Spataro G. Process for the alkoxylation of (per)fluoropolyether alcohols. 2014 WO 2014090649 A1 (assigned to Solvay Specialty Polymers Italy S.P.A).
- [61] Caporiccio G, Strepparola E, Scarati MA. Fluoropolyethers containing end groups endowed with anchoring capacity. 1988 US Patent 4721795 (assigned to Montedison S.P.A).
- [62] Jellali R, Duval JL, Leclerc E. Analysis of the biocompatibility of perfluoropolyether dimethacrylate network using an organotypic method. *Mater Sci Eng C Mater Biol Appl.* 2016;65:295-302.
- [63] Fukushima M, Yamaya M, Yamamoto A, Sato S, Kishita H. Perfluoropolyether rubber composition and ion-conducting polymer electrolyte membrane. 2008 US Patent 20080107950 A1 (assigned to Shin Etsu Chemical Co.).
- [64] Turri S, Barchiesi E. NMR of Perfluoropolyether Diols and Their Acetal Copolymers *Macromolecules* 1995;28 : 7271-7275.
- [65] Lopez G, Guerre M, Schmidt J, Talmon Y, Ladmiral V, Habas J-P, Améduri B. An amphiphilic PEG-*b*-PFPE-*b*-PEG triblock copolymer: synthesis by CuAAC click chemistry and self-assembly in water. *Polym Chem.* 2016; 7: 402-409.
- [66] Li X, McCord EF, Baiagern S, Fox P, Howell JL, Sahoo SK, Rinaldi PL. 2D-NMR studies of a model for Krytox® fluoropolymers. *Magn Reson Chem* 2011;49 : 413–424.

-
- [67] Howell JL, Hofmann MA, Waterfeld A, Sipyagin AM, Friesen CM, Thrasher JS. Reactions of poly-hexafluoropropylene oxide acids and their corresponding salts. *J Fluorine Chem* 1998; 89(1):131-135.
- [68] Dimzon IK, Trier X, Frömel T, Helmus R, Knepper TP, de Voogt P. High Resolution Mass Spectrometry of Polyfluorinated Polyether-Based Formulation. *J Am Soc Mass Spectrom*. 2016;27: 309–318.
- [69] Saprygin AV, Golik VM, Kalashnikov VA, Elistratov OV, Kazantsev MV. Quantification of heavy perfluorinated organics by mass spectrometry. *J Anal Chem* 2010;65(14):1469–1474.
- [70] Kudo T, Macht M, Kuroda M. Laser Desorption Ionization-Time-of-Flight Mass Analysis of Perfluoropolyether Monolayer Directly from Hard Disk. *Anal Chem* 2011;83: 5563–5569.
- [71] Spool AM, Kasai PH. Perfluoropolyethers: analysis by TOF-SIMS. *Macromolecules* 1996;29(5):1691–1697.
- [72] Kostjuk SV, Ortega E, Ganachaud F, Améduri B, Boutevin B. Anionic Ring-Opening Polymerization of Hexafluoropropylene Oxide Using Alkali Metal Fluorides as Catalysts: A Mechanistic Study. *Macromolecules*. 2009; 42 (3):612–619.
- [73] Friesen CM, Jelier BJ. New Methods in Anionic Ring-Opening Polymerization of Fluoro-Epoxides and their Application. *Fluoropolymer 2014 Proceedings, San Diego, USA, October 13-15, 2014*.
- [74] Sianesi D, Zamboni V, Fontanelli R, Binaghi M. Perfluoropolyethers: their physical properties and behavior at high and low temperature. *Wear*. 1971;18:85-100.
- [75] Gunderson RC, Hart AW. *Synthetic Lubricants*. Reinhold: New York, USA;1962.
- [76] Sianesi D, Fontanelli K, Perfluoro polyethers. Their structure and reaction with aluminum chloride. *Makromol Chem*. 1967:102;115-123.
- [77] Montecatini Edison, Div Prod Ind, Tech Inform Bull No 1063.
- [78] Bundesanstalt für Materialprüfung, Berlin 45 Abteilung 4 (Chemische Sicherheitstechnik)
- [79] Pines H, Manassen J. The Mechanism of Dehydration of Alcohols over Alumina Catalysts *Adv Catalysis*. 1966;16:49.
- [80] Richardson RL, Benson SW. A Study of the Surface Acidity of Cracking Catalyst *J Phys Chem*. 1957; 61:405-411.
- [81] Bueche F., *Physical Properties of Polymers*. Interscience, New York, 1962.
- [82] Karis TE, Jhon MS. The relationship between PFPE molecular rheology and tribology. *Tribology Letters*. 1998,5(4):283–286.
- [83] Falcone E. *Chimica Oggi-Chemistry Today*. The Fomblin-Fluorinated Fluids. 1983 8:27-30.
- [84] Ouano AC, Appelt B, Watson TD. Poly(perfluoro ethers): viscosity, density and molecular weight relationships. *Am Chem Soc Org Coat Appl Polym Sci Proc*. 1981;46:230.
- [85] Marchionni G, Ajroldi G, Pezzin G. Molecular weight dependence of some rheological and thermal properties of perfluoropolyethers. *Eur Poly J* 1988 ;24(12):1211-1216.
- [86] Boyer RF. The Relation of Transition Temperatures to Chemical Structure in High Polymers. *Rubber Chem. Technol.*, 1963;36:1320.
- [87] Tonelli C, Valsecchi R, Mashlyakovskiy LN, Khomko EV. Reactive perfluoropolyoxyalkylene oligomers. I. Isothermal equilibrium on silica gel: Fundamental parameters. *J Fluorine Chem*. 2014;161:76-82.
- [88] Valsecchi R, Mutta F, De Patto U, Tonelli C. Countercurrent fractionation of methylol-terminated perfluoropolyoxyalkylene oligomers by supercritical carbon dioxide. *J. of Supercritical Fluids*. 2014; 88:85–91.

-
- [89] Nielsen RP, Valsecchi R, Strandgaard M, Maschietti M. Experimental study on fluid phase equilibria of hydroxyl-terminated perfluoropolyether oligomers and supercritical carbon dioxide. *J of Supercritical Fluids*. 2015;101:124-130.
- [90] Young CJ, Hurely MD, Wallington TJ, Mabury SA. Atmospheric Lifetime and Global Warming Potential of a Perfluoropolyether. *Environ Sci Technol*. 2006;40(7):2242–2246.
- [91] Food and Drug Administration, Regulations 176.160 and 176.170 and effective food contact-notifications (FCN's) USA (2010).
- [92] Food and Drug Administration, 21CFR § 176.170 Components of paper and paperboard in contact with aqueous and fatty foods and §176.180 Components of paper and paperboard in contact with dry food. USA (2010).
- [93] Malinverno G, Pantini G, Bootman J. Safety Evaluation of Perfluoropolyethers, Liquid Polymers used in Barrier Creams and other Skin-care Products. *Food and Chem Toxicology* 1996;34:639-650.
- [94] https://www.ec.gc.ca/lcpecepa/eng/subs_list/DSL/DSLsearch.cfm?critSearch=CAS&critCAS=60164-51-4 (Accessed July 6, 2017).
- [95] Janjic JM, Srinivas M, Kadayakkara DKK, Ahrens ET. Self-delivering nanoemulsions for dual fluorine-19 MRI and fluorescence detection. *J Am Chem Soc* 2008;130 (9):2832-2841.
- [96] Dams R, Hintzer K. Chapter 1 : Industrial Aspects of Fluorinated Oligomers and Polymers, in *Fluorinated Polymers: Volume 2: Applications*. Editors Améduri B and Sawada H. RSC Oxford:UK. 2016 ;2 :1-31.
- [97] Howell, JL, Lu N, Friesen CM, Perez EW, Novak I, Waterfeld A, Thrasher JS. The Preparation of Primary Poly-Hexafluoropropylene Oxide Halides (Poly-HFPO-CF₂X where X = I, Br, Cl and F). *J Fluorine Chem*. 2004;125(10) :1513-1518.
- [98] Wlassics I, Tortelli V. Synthesis of α, ω -perfluoropolyether iodides. *J Fluorine Chem*. 2005;126(1):45-51.
- [99] Howell JL, Pérez EW, Waterfeld A, Friesen CM, Thrasher JS, Nowak I. Perfluoropolyether primary bromides and iodides. 2006 US Patent 7148385 B2. (assigned to DuPont).
- [100] Tanesi D, Pasetti A, Corti C. 1969 Fluorinated oxygen containing acyl fluorides. 1969 US Patent 3,442,942 (assigned to Montefluos).
- [101] Sianesi D, Pasetti A, Belardinello G. High molecular weight polymeric perfluorinated copolyethers and process for the preparation from tetrafluoroethylene. 1984 US Patent 4,451,646 A (assigned to Montedison).
- [102] Yang Y-W, Hentschel J, Chen Y-C, Lazari M, Zeng H, van Dam M, Guan Z. "Clicked" fluoropolymer elastomers as robust materials for potential microfluidic device applications. *J Mater Chem*. 2012;22(3):1100-1106.
- [103] Corveleyn SG, Dahlke GD, Dams RJ, Grootaert WMA, Guerra MA, Manzara AP, Opstel T. Fluoroether based elastomers having low glass transition temperature. 2014 WO2014/055,406 2014 (assigned to 3M).
- [104] Lopez G, Ameduri B, Habas J-P. A Versatile Strategy to Synthesize Perfluoropolyether-Based Thermoplastic Fluoropolymers by Alkyne-Azide Step-Growth Polymerization. *Macromol Rapid Commun* 2016;37 :711-717.
- [105] Guarda PA, Picozzi R, Simeone G. Amino derivatives of perfluoropolyethers. 2016 WO2016079053 (assigned to Solvay Specialty Polymers).
- [106] Di Meo A, Picozzi R, Tonelli C. Process for the preparation of perfluoropolyethers having aldehyde, alcohol, amine end groups by catalytic reduction. 2006 US Patent 6984759 B2 (assigned to Solvay Solexis).

-
- [107] Wadgaonkar P, Menon S, Tonelli CAP. Process for the manufacture of functional PFPE derivatives. 2010 EP2417184 A; WO 2010/115852010 (assigned to Solvay Solexis).
- [108] Wongchitphimon S, Wang R, Jiratananon R. Surface modification of polyvinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene (PVDF-HFP) hollow fiber membrane for membrane gas absorption. *J Membr Sci.* 2011;381(1–2):183-191.
- [109] Bartlett PL. Perfluoroalkyletheramidoalkyltriakoxysilanes. 1972 US Patent 3,646,085 (assigned to DuPont).
- [110] Wong DHC, Thelen JL, Fuc Y, Devaux D, Pandya AA, Battaglia VS, Balsara NP, DeSimone JM. Nonflammable perfluoropolyether-based electrolytes for lithium batteries. *Proc Natl Acad Sci.* 2014;111(9):3327–3331.
- [111] Zhou Z, Dominey RN, Rolland JP, Maynor BW, Pandya AA, DeSimone JM. Molded, High Surface Area Polymer Electrolyte Membranes from Cured Liquid Precursors. *J Am Chem Soc.* 2006;128 (39):12963–12972.
- [112] Tonelli C, Trombetta T, Scicchitano M, Castiglioni G. New perfluoropolyether soft segment containing polyurethanes. *J Appl Polym Sci.* 1995;57(9):1031-1042.
- [113] Meijs GF, Laycock BG, Griffiths MC, Cheong E. Perfluoroalkylether macromer having two polymerizable groups. 1999 US Patent 5,962,611 A (assigned to Novartis AG and Industrial Research Organization).
- [114] Turri S, Radice S, Canteri R, Speranza G, Anderle M. Surface study of perfluoropolyether–urethane cross-linked polymers. *Surface and Interface Analysis.* 2000;29(12):873-886.
- [115] Temtchenko T, Turri S, Novelli S, Delucchi M. New developments in perfluoropolyether resins technology: high solid and durable polyurethanes for heavy duty and clear OEM coatings. *Prog Org Coat.* 2001;43(1–3):75-84.
- [116] Turri S, Scicchitano M, Marchetti R, Sanguineti A, Radice S. Chapter 9: Structure-Property Relationships of Coatings based on perfluoropolyether macromers. *Fluoropolymers 2, properties.* Eds. Hougham G, Cassidy PE, Johns K, Davidson T. Kluwer Academic/Plenum Publishers, New York, New York. 1999:145-169.
- [117] Li G, Char K, Wie J-J, Nguyen NA, Mackay ME, Chung WJ, Pyun J, Kim ET. Synthesis, Self-Assembly and Reversible Healing of Supramolecular Perfluoropolyethers. *J Poly Sci, Part A: Poly Chem.* 2013;51:3598–3606.
- [118] Pilati F, Toselli M, Vallieri A, Tonelli C. Synthesis of polyesters-perfluoropolyethers block copolymers. *Polymer Bulletin.* 1992; 28(2) :151–157.
- [119] Levi M, Turri S. Equilibrium and non-equilibrium polycondensation process of segmented poly-perfluoro(oxymethylene-*ran*-oxyethylene)-carbonates. *J Fluorine Chem.* 2004;125:339–344.
- [120] Patrick MJ, Janjic JM, Teng H, O’Hear MR, Brown CW, Stokum JA, Schmidt BF, Ahrens ET, Waggoner AS. Intracellular pH Measurements Using Perfluorocarbon Nanoemulsions. *J Am Chem Soc.* 2013;135(49):18445–18457.
- [121] Tonelli C, Di Meo A, Fontana S, Russo A. Perfluoropolyether functional oligomers: unusual reactivity in organic chemistry. *J Fluorine Chem.* 2002;118(1–2):107-121.
- [122] Bongiovanni R, Di Meo A, Pollicino A, Priola A, Tonelli C. New perfluoropolyether urethane methacrylates as surface modifiers: Effect of molecular weight and end group structure. *React Func Polym.* 2008;68(1):189-200.
- [123] Priola A, Bongiovanni R, Malucelli G, Pollicino A, Tonelli C, Simeone G. UV-curable systems containing perfluoropolyether structures: Synthesis and characterisation. *Macromol Chem Phys.* 1997;198(6):1893-1907.

-
- [124] Bongiovanni R, Malucelli G, Pollicino A, Tonelli C, Simeone G, Priola A. Perfluoropolyether structures as surface modifying agents of UV-curable systems. *Macromol Chem Phys.* 1998;199(6):1099-1105
- [125] Vitale A, Priola A, Tonelli C, Bongiovanni R. Nanoheterogeneous networks by photopolymerization of perfluoropolyethers and acrylic co-monomers. *Polym Int.* 2013;62(9):1395-1401.
- [126] Rolland JP, Hagberg EC, Denison GM, Carter KR, De Simone JM. High-Resolution Soft Lithography: Enabling Materials for Nanotechnologies. *Angew Chem Int Ed.* 2004;43(43):5796-5799.
- [127] Rolland JP, Van Dam RM, Schorzman DA, Quake SR, DeSimone JM. Solvent-Resistant Photocurable "Liquid Teflon" for Microfluidic Device Fabrication. *J Am Chem Soc.* 2004;126(8):2322-2323.
- [128] Williams SS, Retterer S, Lopez R, Ruiz R, Samulski ET, DeSimone JM. High-Resolution PFPE-based Molding Techniques for Nanofabrication of High-Pattern Density, Sub-20 nm Features: A Fundamental Materials Approach. *Nano Letters.* 2010;10(4):1421-1428.
- [129] Bongiovanni R, Medici A, Zompatori A, Garavaglia S, Tonelli C. Perfluoropolyether polymers by UV curing: design, synthesis and characterization. *Polym Int.* 2012;61(1):65-73
- [130] Vitale A, Bongiovanni R, Ameduri B. Fluorinated Oligomers and Polymers in Photopolymerization. *Chem Rev.* 2015;115 (16):8835–8866.
- [131] Hu Z, Chen L, Betts DE, Pandya A, Hillmyer MA, DeSimone JM. Optically Transparent, Amphiphilic Networks Based on Blends of Perfluoropolyethers and Poly(ethylene glycol). *J Am Chem Soc.* 2008;130:14244–14252.
- [132] Lombardi V, Bongiovanni R, Malucelli G, Priola A, Garavaglia S, Turri S. New acrylic-allylic resins containing perfluoropolyether chains for UV-cured coatings. *Pigm Resin Technol.* 1999;28:212-216.
- [133] De Marco C, Gaidukeviciute A, Kiyani R, Eaton SM, Levi M, Osellame R, Chichkov BN, Turri S. A New Perfluoropolyether-Based Hydrophobic and Chemically Resistant Photoresist Structured by Two-Photon Polymerization. *Langmuir* 2013; 29:426–431.
- [134] Lopez G, Guerre M, Améduri B, Habas J-P, Ladmiral V. Photocrosslinked PVDF-based star polymer coatings: an all-in-one alternative to PVDF/PMMA blends for outdoor applications. *Polym Chem.* 2017;8:3045-3049.
- [135] <http://www.solvay.com/en/markets-and-products/featured-products/Fluorolink.html> (accessed June 30, 2017)
- [136] Song J, Ye Q, Lee WT, Wang X, He T, Shah KW, Xu J. Perfluoropolyether/poly(ethylene glycol) triblock copolymers with controllable self-assembly behaviour for highly efficient anti-bacterial materials. *RSC Adv.* 2015;5:64170-64179.
- [137] Kressler J, Kaiser S. Amphiphilic block copolymers having water soluble and perfluoroalkyl-group containing blocks. *Polymer Preprints* 2005; 46(2):580.
- [138] Taribagil RR, Hillmyer MA, Lodge TP. Hydrogels from ABA and ABC Triblock Polymers. *Macromolecules.* 2010;43:5396–5404.
- [139] Messori M, Toselli M, Pilati F, Fabbri P, Tonelli C. Poly(ϵ -caprolactone)-poly(fluoroalkylene oxide)-poly(ϵ -caprolactone) block copolymers as surface modifiers of poly(vinyl chloride). *Surface Coatings International Part B: Coatings Transactions.* 2002; 85:197.
- [140] Singh A, Naskar A, Haynes D, Drews M, Smith Jr. DW. Synthesis, Characterization and Surface Properties of poly(lactic acid)– perfluoropolyether Block Copolymers. *Polym Int.* 2011;60 :507–516.

-
- [141] Haynes D, Drews M, Naskar AK, Harrison G, Singh A, Yang C-C, Smith Jr. DW. Poly(L-lactic acid) with Segmented Perfluoropolyether Enchainment. *Macromolecules*. 2007;40:9354-9360.
- [142] Bertolotti B, Messaoudi H, Chikh L, Vancaeyzeele C, Alfonsi S, Fichet O. Stability in alkaline aqueous electrolyte of air electrode protected with Fluorinated interpenetrating polymer network membrane. *J Power Sources*. 2015; 274:488-495.
- [143] Hu Z, Pitet LM, Hillmyer MA, DeSimone JM. High Modulus, Low Surface Energy, Photochemically Cured Materials from Liquid Precursors. *Macromolecules*. 2010;43:10397-10405.
- [144] Wolfgang H. Binder WH. Sachsenhofer R. 'Click' Chemistry in Polymer and Material Science: An Update. *Macromol. Rapid Commun*. 2008;29:952-981.
- [145] Charlas M, Martineau CDHE, Lopez GPM, Habas JP, Ameduri B. Matériaux Réticulés Thermodurcissables à Basse T_g et Thermostables à base d' Unités Fluoroéthers 2016 ; FR2016/051678 (assigned to Labinal Power System and Université de Montpellier et CNRS)
- [146] Charlas M, Martineau CDHE, Lopez GPM, Habas JP, Ameduri B. Perfluoroether Unit-based thermostability, low T_g thermoplastic and thermosetting cross-linked materials (English). 2017 WO 2017001806 A1 (assigned to Labinal Power System and Université de Montpellier et CNRS).
- [147] Osawa Y, Sato S, Matsuda T. Fluororubber composition and its production. 2000 JP-A 2000-007835 (assigned to Shin Etsu Chemical Co. Ltd).
- [148] Osawa Y, Sato S, Matsuda T. Fluororubber composition. JP-A 2001-106893(assigned to Shin Etsu Chemical Co. Ltd).
- [149] Matsuda T, Osawa Y, Koike N, Sakano Y. Fluororubber composition and its cured product. 2003 JP-A 2003-201401(assigned to Shin Etsu Chemical Co. Ltd).
- [150] Sommer K, Kaiser S, Krylova OO, Kressler J, Pohl P, Busse K. Influence of Amphiphilic Block Copolymer Induced Changes in Membrane Ion Conductance on the Reversal of Multidrug Resistance. *J Med Chem*. 2008;51(14):4253-4259.
- [151] Charlas M, Martineau CDHE, Lopez GPM, Habas JP, Ameduri B. Copolymères Thermoplastiques à Basse T_g et Thermostables à base d' Unités Perfluoroéthers (Français) or Perfluoroether Unit-based thermostability, low T_g thermoplastic polymers (English). 2017 WO 2017001807 A1 (assigned to Labinal Power System, Université de Montpellier et CNRS).
- [152] Lopez G. Ameduri B, Habas J-P. A Perfluoropolyether-Based Elastomers Library With On-Demand Thermorheological Features. *European Polymer Journal* 2017;95:207-215.
- [153] Sackmann EK, Fulton AL, Beebe DJ. The present and future role of microfluidics in biomedical research. *Nature*. 2014 ;507 :181-189.
- [154] Nge PN, Rogers CI, Woolley AT. Advances in Microfluidic Materials, Functions, Integration, and Applications. *Chem Rev*. 2013;113(4):2550-2583.
- [155] De Marco C, Mele E, Camposeo A, Stabile R, Cingolani R, Pisignano D. Organic light-emitting nanofibers by solvent-resistant nanofluids. *Adv Mater*. 2008;20(21):4158-4164.
- [156] Vitale A, Quaglio M, Marasso SL, Chiodoni A, Cocuzza M, Bongiovanni R. Direct photolithography of perfluoropolyethers for solvent-resistant microfluidics. *Langmuir*. 2013; 29:15711-15718.
- [157] Bong KW, Leeac J, Doyle PS. Stop flow lithography in perfluoropolyether (PFPE) microfluidic channels. *Lab Chip*. 2014;14:4680-4687.
- [158] Oldani V, Sergi G, Pirola C, Sacchi B, Bianchi CL. Sol-gel hybrid coatings containing silica and a perfluoropolyether derivative with high resistance and anti-fouling properties in liquid media. *J Fluorine Chem*. 2016;188:43-49.

-
- [159] Messori M, Fabbri P, Pilati F, Tonelli C, Toselli M. Perfluoropolyether-based organic-inorganic coatings. *Progress in Organic Coatings*. 2011;72:461–468.
- [160] Susoof M, Siegman K, Pfaffenroth C, Hirayama M. Evaluation of icephobic coatings—Screening of different coatings and influence of roughness. *Applied Surface Science* 2013; 282: 870-879.
- [161] Zhang L, Zhou Z, Cheng B, DeSimone JM, Samulski ET. Superhydrophobic Behavior of a Perfluoropolyether Lotus-Leaf-like Topography. *Langmuir*. 2006; 22(20): 8576–8580.
- [162] Wong TS, Kang SH, Tang SK, Smythe EJ, Hatton BD, Grinthal A, Aizenberg J. Bioinspired self-repairing slippery surfaces with pressure-stable omniphobicity. *Nature*. 2011;477(7365):443-447.
- [163] Yao X, Dunn SS, Kim P, Duffy M, Alvarenga J, Aizenberg J. Fluorogel Elastomers with Tunable Transparency, Elasticity, Shape-Memory, and Antifouling Properties. *Angew Chem Int Ed*. 2014;53(17):4418-4422.
- [164] Manna U, Raman N, Welsh MA, Zayas-Gonzalez YM, Blackwell HE, Palecek SP, Lynn DM Slippery Liquid-Infused Porous Surfaces that Prevent Microbial Surface Fouling and Kill Non-Adherent Pathogens in Surrounding Media: A Controlled Release Approach. *Adv Funct Mater*. 2016;26:3599–3611.
- [165] Urata C, Dunderdale GJ, England MW, Hozumi A. Self-lubricating organogels (SLUGs) with exceptional syneresis-induced anti-sticking properties against viscous emulsions and ices. *J Mater Chem A*. 2015;3 :12626.
- [166] Ko D-H, Tumbleston JR, Henderson KJ, Euliss LE, DeSimone JM, Lopez R, Samulski ET. Biomimetic microlens array with antireflective “moth-eye” surface. *Soft Matter*. 2011;7:6404-6407.
- [167] Jia R-P, Zong A-X, He X-Y, Xu J-Y, Huang M-S. Synthesis of newly fluorinated thermoplastic polyurethane elastomers and their blood compatibility. *Fibers and Polymers*. 2015;16(2):31.
- [168] Chintapalli M, Timachova K, Olson KR, Mecham SJ, Devaux D, DeSimone JM, Balsara NP. Relationship between Conductivity, Ion Diffusion, and Transference Number in Perfluoropolyether Electrolytes. *Macromolecules*. 2016;49(9):3508–3515.
- [169] Wong DHC, Hallinan DT, Resnick PR, Vitale A, Thelen JL, Meyer TJ, DeSimone JM. Phase Behavior and Electrochemical Characterization of Blends of Perfluoropolyether, Poly(ethylene glycol), and a Lithium Salt. *Chem Mater*. 2015;27(2) :597–603.
- [170] Gilles S, Diez M, Offenhausser A, Lensen MC, Mayer D. Deformation of nanostructures on polymer molds during soft UV nanoimprint lithography. *Nanotechnology* 2010;21:245307.
- [171] Kelly JY, DeSimone JM. Shape-Specific, Monodisperse Nano-Molding of Protein Particles. *J Am Chem Soc*. 2008;130(16):5438–5439.
- [172] De Marco C, Eaton SM, Levi M, Cerullo G, Turri S, Osellame R. High-Fidelity Solvent-Resistant Replica Molding of Hydrophobic Polymer Surfaces Produced by Femtosecond Laser Nanofabrication. *Langmuir*. 2011;27(13):8391-8395.
- [173] Ahrens ET, Flores R, Xu H, Morel PA. In vivo imaging platform for tracking immunotherapeutic cells. *Nature Biotechnology*. 2005;23 :983-987.
- [174] O’Hanlon CE, Amede KG, O’Hear MR, Janjic JM. NIR-labeled perfluoropolyether nanoemulsions for drug delivery and imaging. *J Fluorine Chem*. 2012;137:27–33.